

Requirements for Certification of ECRIN Data Centres with Explanation and Elaboration Standards

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Requirements for Certification of ECRIN Data Centres
with
Explanation and Elaboration of Standards, Version 5.0
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Preface

This is version 5.0 of the ‘Requirements for certification of data centres’, published by ECRIN, the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (the first version was produced in 2011, the second in 2012, third in 2015, and fourth in 2018). The requirements are the criteria used by ECRIN to identify, and then certify, clinical trials units that can provide high-quality, compliant and safe data management, as well as effective management of the underlying systems and IT infrastructure.

This latest version results from a review in 2022/23 by members of ECRIN’s data centre Certification Board and invited experts. The full list of contributors is provided on page iv.

Over and above their use for certification, the requirements are intended to describe good practice in data and IT management in clinical research, and in clinical trials in particular. They were developed by senior staff working in non-commercial clinical trials units in Europe, and are intended as a practical guide for staff working in IT and data management in that sector (though the same principles apply to all clinical research environments).

The 126 requirements, or standards, included in the current version are divided into 19 separate lists, focused on IT, data management, the more generic aspects of trial management, and – new in this version – statistical programming. Each standard has a code, a title, and a single statement summarising the requirement. This document provides, in addition, explanatory and elaboration material that attempts to clarify the meaning of each statement, and/or give examples of its application, and which also indicates the evidence that would normally be used to assess a unit’s compliance. The document also includes a brief introduction to the standards and their development, including a description of the ECRIN Data Centres audit process, a glossary of terms, and a summary of the main changes from the previous version.

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Introduction and Background

This document describes the systems and functionality that a non-commercial clinical trials unit needs to demonstrate if it is to become certified as an 'ECRIN Data Centre'. It does so by listing a series of standards – dealing with IT systems, data management (DM) practices, treatment allocation and statistical programming – all indicative of safe, effective and compliant data storage and data processing.

The 126 standards are divided into 19 different sections, each dealing with a particular topic. Each section is prefaced by a short statement clarifying the scope of the standards within it, or discussing some general issues about those standards.

Each standard is then presented, along with some 'Explanation and Elaboration' (E&E) material (this term borrowed from the Consort initiative [1]). This material has been added to clarify what the standard means, for instance by providing examples, and to describe the evidence that would normally be required to demonstrate compliance. In a few cases additional material has been added at the end of a section to discuss best practice in that area, over and above the ECRIN requirements.

The focus of the standards, the audit and the certification is the IT and data management activities of a clinical research unit, even though that unit will usually be involved in many other aspects of the research process – writing protocols, gaining regulatory and ethics approvals, analysing results, publishing papers, etc. This is why throughout the document the research unit is referred to as a 'data centre', or more often just the 'centre'. It is the IT and data management services that the unit can provide, for itself, for external sponsors, and potentially for other research units, which are under consideration.

Certification as an ECRIN data centre provides a public indicator or 'badge' of quality, backed up by public standards and a rigorous assessment procedure. ECRIN maintains and publicises a central list of data centres and encourages sponsors of ECRIN-supported trials to use those centres to provide the data management infrastructure for their trials.

Origin and development of the standards

The standards are based upon the principles laid out in the International Conference on Harmonisation's guidelines on Good Clinical Practice (ICH GCP [2]).

In many cases, however, these guidelines, as applied to IT systems and data management (DM), are rather vague. Working within the EU FP funded project ECRIN-PPI (2008–2011), ECRIN's Working Party 10, therefore, developed a set of more detailed, pragmatic IT and DM specific standards for trials units, using the

GCP guidelines as a starting point, but also considering many other international and national documents and regulations. The rationale for the standards and the way in which they were developed is described in more detail in [3].

The original version of the standards was piloted in audits at Düsseldorf and Uppsala in November 2011. Further revisions followed – a description of the revision process for v2.2 can be found in [4] (also translated into French [5]) – incorporating feedback from auditors, certification board members, and from specially invited experts in clinical trials IT systems.

The assessment process

ECRIN standards are designed to be used as the basis of an on-site audit by appointed ECRIN auditors. They are also designed to be used by units for self-assessment purposes, and as a general guide to what is considered to be good quality practice in clinical research IT and data management. The emphasis is on clinical trials in the non-commercial sector, but the same principles apply to data management in non-interventional studies, and indeed to clinical research in any context.

ECRIN audits are planned to last up to three days, and normally involve a team of three auditors, all of whom are experienced trials unit staff. The audit results and auditors' recommendations are sent first to the audited unit (to allow them to comment and correct any factual errors) and are then passed to ECRIN's Independent Certification Board (ICB), who make the final decision about the certification of a unit as an ECRIN data centre. The audit is normally conducted in English, but ECRIN tries to ensure that the audit team includes at least one individual who can speak, natively, the language of the data centre, so that all evidence can be inspected.

A centre will be awarded certification if the ICB is confident all standards have been met. If most of the standards have been achieved, and the auditors estimate that the remainder could be met within a reasonable time, the ICB may request later written evidence, or a follow-up re-audit, to confirm that the required 'corrective and preventative actions' (CAPA) have been carried out, after which they will reconsider the certification decision. Otherwise the unit will need to reapply at a later date.

Clinical trials processes and procedures are (or should be) under continuous development and so ECRIN audits focus on recent activity, and trials that have begun recently, usually within the last 12 to 24 months.

Auditors will expect to see a fully developed quality management system within any candidate unit, with current SOPs and other controlled documents describing most

of the areas covered by the standards. Such documents are not sufficient, however – evidence will also be sought of these controlled documents being implemented in practice, by examining trial-specific documentation and logs, validation records, agreements, meeting minutes, emails, etc., as well as interviewing staff. Direct inspection of the centre’s systems, especially the clinical data management system (usually only with dummy or test data) will also be required.

Note that the auditors expect to see trial-specific processes (as described in current quality documents such as SOPs) demonstrated in the context of at least two trials.

The specific evidence that would be expected for each standard is included in this document as part of the Explanation and Elaboration material. This describes only the most common evidence that auditors would expect to see and in any particular case there may be more appropriate evidence available, more relevant to the particular situation of a specific data centre. The references to expected evidence should, therefore, only be seen as a guide and not as absolute requirements.

Subcontracting and organisational responsibilities

In some cases, part or all of the functionality covered by a standard may not be the direct responsibility of the trials unit itself, e.g. it may be provided by the parent organisation, or a commercial host, or another collaborating trials unit. Common examples are:

- IT infrastructure services provided by a university or hospital central IT department, rather than being housed within the trials unit itself.
- A SaaS (software as a service) version of a clinical data management system, where the system and the clinical data are hosted externally and all access, from the data centre as well as the clinical sites, is via the web.

In such circumstances it is important to remember that if the sponsor has delegated the responsibility for IT and data management to the data centre, *the centre still retains that responsibility* even if it has itself delegated some functions to others. That means *that the centre must itself monitor its own service suppliers*, to ensure that their activity is regulatory compliant and functioning as it should be.

The recently revised version of the ICH’s guidance document for Good Clinical Practice, E6 (R2), makes this point explicitly:

“The sponsor should ensure oversight of any trial-related duties and functions carried out on its behalf, including trial-related duties and functions that are subcontracted to another party by the sponsor’s contracted CRO(s).” [6]

In this context the data centres are taking the role of ‘sponsor’s contracted CRO(s)’, and given that in most situations the sponsor also delegates the responsibility ‘to ensure oversight’ to the contracted CROs, the data centre now needs to make sure this happens to remain GCP compliant.

Unfortunately, the evidence is that oversight is not always performed as rigorously as it should be. The Inspectors Working Group of the European Medicines Agency has listed a wide range of issues it has discovered in respect of subcontracted services [7], including missing or out of date contractual agreements, poor definition of the distribution of tasks, lack of understanding of the location of data, a lack of understanding of GCP obligations by subcontractors, unwillingness to accept audits, poor understanding of reporting requirements, and confusion over outputs and actions to be taken at the end of the trial.

Similar problems have been found within ECRIN audits, especially with regard to subcontracted IT infrastructure. Centres sometimes appear too willing to ‘leave it to the IT people’, with the result that they often poorly understand, and do not monitor activities like backup and restore testing, ongoing system validation, and system patching and updating, even though they are still responsible for the proper execution of all these tasks.

ECRIN standards make clear that, even if a centre is not carrying out the operational day-to-day tasks involved in an activity because they have subcontracted it to some other organisation, or some other part of their own organisation, they remain responsible for its proper operation and must provide evidence that:

- the subcontracting organisation is performing its operations to the standard required;
- ‘the standard required’ is based on a written and mutually understood definition of responsibilities; and
- the data centre has an oversight mechanism in place to ensure that the standard is being met.

An ‘oversight mechanism’ means more than having good contractual agreements and SLAs in place, or even doing an initial supplier audit (though all of those are very useful) – it implies an ongoing risk-based process of monitoring and/or periodic review. That in turn demands well defined communication channels, with clear understanding by all parties of the responsibilities of each, and a willingness by subcontractors to support the compliance needs of the data centres [8].

This point is reiterated and expanded upon in the Explanation and Elaboration material for many individual standards, especially those dealing with IT, but the general principle applies to all types of activity and all of the standards.

Device management

A new IT section has been added to cover the management of user devices and risks associated with such devices, particularly those resulting from external threats such as viruses/malware, ongoing patching and disposal.

Statistical programming

Treatment allocation (TA) standards covering randomisation, minimisation, and supporting systems have been brought into the main body of the standards, but remain optional. They are provided for self-assessment and/or inclusion in the ECRIN audit discussion if a unit wishes.

If a unit decided, however, that it wished to provide TA services to ECRIN-supported trials (or act as the 'lead CTU' in those trials, which would normally include the TA function), ECRIN would then use these standards to assess the quality of treatment allocation systems, independently of any decision about data centre certification.

A new section has been added in response to increasing inspection focus on statistical programming and its reproducibility. This covers validation of data transfer, statistical software, and custom programs.

The standards – terminology and phrasing

The following 19 sections list the 126 ECRIN standards. In each case the standard code and title are followed by the requirement statement in bold text. The Explanation and Elaboration material, usually with notes on expected evidence, is provided below.

Note that several common terms (e.g. 'Centre', 'Site', 'Controlled documents') have specific meanings within these standards and the support material. In addition a few terms (e.g. CDMA) have been developed specifically for the standards. Please refer to the glossary at the end of this document for definitions of the terms used and explanations of abbreviations.

The standards are expressed in a variety of ways: 'the centre should...', 'the centre can...', 'documents exist...', 'mechanisms are in place...', etc. For the avoidance of doubt, in each case the standard is actually expressing an imperative: the various phrases are all equivalent to 'must'.

GE01: Centre staff training and support

The standards in this section are concerned with the initial and ongoing training and support for the data management and IT staff who directly support the data centre. In most cases such staff will be based in the centre, though some IT staff may be based in IT host organisations. The standards do not apply to site-based staff – training and support for these is dealt with in Section DM04.

During an audit the focus will be on the IT/DM staff and the documentation (e.g. training records) associated with them. The expectation would be, however, that the controlled documents and processes concerned with training and support would apply to all centre staff. There is no requirement for IT/data management-specific policies or procedures.

GE01.01: Policies for training

Controlled documents are in place describing initial and continuing training requirements, policies and procedures.

Having properly trained and competent staff managing trials and related systems is a GCP requirement. While it is not possible or appropriate for auditors to assess the competence of staff in the course of a short audit, it is possible for them to check that a centre has the proper mechanisms in place to promote and monitor staff competence.

Appropriate controlled documents should, therefore, exist that cover this area, detailing how initial training (or ‘induction’) as well as ongoing training should be identified, organised, signed off and recorded.

The expectation would be that initial and ongoing training had been tailored to the individual’s role as well as their previous experience, that the SOPs and other controlled documents relevant to each role had been identified, that a mechanism existed to ensure that staff were familiar with the procedures and systems relevant to them, and that any changes in those procedures or systems were transmitted to the appropriate staff.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be the controlled documents themselves.

GE01.02: Documentation of training

Records of initial and continuing training and development are kept for all IT and DM staff.

All training should be documented to show that staff have been properly prepared for their role. This includes the initial training of new staff, as well as ongoing courses, study days, workshops, webinars, etc. Initial training records should normally show how and when the role holder become familiar with the SOPs and

controlled documents relevant to them, and include a final appraisal or 'sign-off' that clearly indicates the end of the initial training period.

Although some generally applicable training input (e.g. GCP updates) may be organised and recorded on a unit-wide basis, in most cases it is far better to document training on an individual basis – for example using a separate folder for each member of staff. This is more flexible, allows greater detail to be captured, and allows training to be monitored much more easily (see GE01.03).

Training records should include, as a minimum, the dates and titles of training, but details such as duration and training provider are also useful. Individual folders can often include attendance certificates and programme details as well, and may be combined with job description(s), CVs, records of publications, etc., to create a comprehensive training and development portfolio. Such folders could be held and maintained centrally or by the members of staff themselves.

The training of IT staff associated with (but often not part of) the trials unit should ensure that they are also aware of the additional data protection and GCP requirements linked to handling clinical trial data, at least as they apply to their role.

NB Although the standard is specifically about IT and data management staff, it is expected that training systems would be the same for all staff within each of the relevant departments in the organisation.

Evidence that this standard has been met would be the training records themselves.

GE01.03: Managing training requirements

Mechanisms exist to review, plan and document training and development for individual IT and DM staff, with the time between successive reviews not normally being greater than one year.

Training requirements change as a function of both general or organisational change (e.g. revised regulations or new systems) and individual development. In addition, training may not always be possible when initially scheduled, or become irrelevant or superseded.

Training and development needs must, therefore, be kept under review, and to be effective this must be done on an individual basis. A mechanism to identify needs and requests should exist and the results of that process should be documented.

In many units this will form part of an annual staff appraisal, but in others it may be part of an annual exercise in setting and allocating training budgets. The requirement for an annual review is a minimum – there will be many situations when changes in an individual's role generates a training or development need on an ad hoc basis.

As with GE01.02, the use of individual training folders or portfolios makes the training review process much easier to both manage and document.

Evidence the standard has been met would come from inspection of the relevant records, as well as discussions with staff.

GE01.04: Whistleblowing

A mechanism should be in place to provide staff with an alternative pathway to seek advice with ethical or legal concerns, if a discussion with a line manager or trial management group does not resolve an issue.

In almost all cases a member of staff would initially escalate any such issue to their line manager, and/or the trial management group, and the issue would be investigated and resolved – at least in the sense that trials unit staff all agreed on the chosen response and the reasons for it.

Very rarely, however, a member of staff may feel that the concerns they have raised have not been taken seriously (or perhaps even believed) by their line manager or the management group to which they have reported their concerns, or that the response has been inadequate.

In such a situation there should be a recognised escalation pathway outside the normal reporting hierarchy and staff should be aware that it exists and how to access it, ideally as part of their initial unit induction. This might be via a particular office/post within the parent university or hospital, or direct to a sponsor representative (if external to the trials unit).

This standard does not relate to ‘ordinary’ disputes between staff and their managers, for example about conditions of work, inappropriate requests, etc., which would need to be resolved by the relevant disciplinary and grievance procedures and the human resources department.

The standard does relate, however, to the need for a unit to accept that – however rarely it might be needed – it is necessary to set up an alternative escalation pathway that does not use the normal management hierarchy. Otherwise the power structure within the unit both investigates and judges every issue without any appeal mechanism, which could potentially lead to the abuse of participants, and/or wasted research effort. It is accepted completely that the need for such a pathway to be used would be very rare, but it is not sufficient for the unit simply to claim that it would never arise.

Evidence that this standard is met would largely come from interviewing staff, discussing and clarifying the escalation pathways available and how staff are made aware of them. Although a unit may not have a formal controlled document dealing

with this issue, some form of information (e.g. as a document for new staff, or on a web page) should be available to all staff describing the options available to them.

IT01: Management of IT infrastructure

The standards in this section are concerned with the servers and related hardware (e.g. network storage) that support the core IT functionality of the data centre. They cover the location, management and support of this central infrastructure through its life cycle, and the management of the physical environment in which that hardware is installed, normally a 'server room' or third-party data centre facility, including protection from intrusion, environmental threats such as fire, and system threats such as a power loss.

The use of commercial data centre facilities is likely to offer a higher degree of security and resilience for computer infrastructure than may be available at the trials unit, e.g. use of mirroring over multiple geographical sites, backup power supplies. Such services should be considered with due regard for legal jurisdictions noted in IT01.01 below. Use of high-quality local infrastructure hosting facilities remains acceptable.

Certification against formal quality standards such as ISO 27001, SOC 2 etc., would be expected for commercial data centres.

Whatever the distribution of responsibilities for infrastructure management, it will be the responsibility of the data centre to have all relevant evidence available during an audit, even if it has not produced that evidence itself. The centre may, therefore, need to gather material from its service providers beforehand and/or arrange that staff and facilities from those service providers are available during an audit.

Contractual and service level agreements (SLAs) between the centre and service suppliers may form part of the evidence for these standards, but the centre should be able to show that such agreements are actually being met – i.e. there is an expectation that a centre will monitor and document the performance of its service providers.

Note that management of user devices such as laptop and desktop PCs is covered by IT07 below.

IT01.01: Infrastructure location

Data storage and processing locations, including for backed up and mirrored data, must be known to the centre and the facilities used must meet all legal requirements for data protection.

If a centre manages its own servers, or they are housed within its own parent organisation, it should be straightforward to show compliance with this standard – the locations of the data will be known, and any local data centre will need to meet

the local legal requirements. The centre must be able to demonstrate compliance with EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [9].

If a third-party data processing service is used, e.g. a SaaS CDMS, the centre must be clear exactly where the data is located, and in particular if it is in the European Economic Area (EEA) or not. The same applies to backup or 'mirrored' copies of data. If not in the EEA, the centre needs to know, and show, that the physical and logical security requirements in place are at least equal to those demanded by the EEA (see EU adequacy decisions [17] and developing Trans-Atlantic Data Privacy Framework [18] between the EU and US). This is because the GDPR imposes the same requirements on data controllers and data processors, if managing data about European citizens, wherever in the world that data is stored. The centre should also ensure, in these circumstances, that the patient information sheets a) clearly state that the data is stored outside the EEA, and b) provide an outline of how GDPR compliance has been assured (this level of transparency being itself a requirement under the GDPR).

The evidence in such cases would be the written assurances and explanations received from SaaS suppliers guaranteeing GDPR compliance, plus example patient information sheets.

NB Because both institutions and national governments may change the rules regarding sensitive personal data and where it can be stored, and because the interpretation of those rules may also change, especially if challenged in the courts, ECRIN recommends that EU-based researchers do not store sensitive data outside of the EEA unless it is encrypted and the data centre itself controls the encryption process.

Encryption provided by the infrastructure or software vendor is still vulnerable to internal attack from the infrastructure or vendor staff, so only self-managed encryption is as secure as a local installation. But managing encryption (e.g. keeping a hierarchy of encryption keys secure, testing decryption mechanisms), especially over a long period, is not a trivial process. Although self-managed encryption does provide the freedom to store data anywhere, including on relatively cheap public clouds, the costs and effort involved should not be underestimated.

IT01.02: Secured server room

Computer infrastructure must be securely housed in a commercial data centre or local facility, with access limited to specific roles, and with access arrangements known to the centre.

All servers, and related equipment such as SANs and routers, must be located in a locked room, or rooms, specifically allocated for that purpose.

The centre, even if it does not manage the server room(s) directly, should still know who is able to have unescorted access to the rooms (not the individuals, but the names of roles or teams with such access). These would generally be a small subgroup of the IT staff, but it might include senior maintenance or security staff. The centre should also know the procedures for gaining access to the server rooms, and the possible reasons for access, logging arrangements etc., and be happy that those arrangements represent sufficient physical security.

If the centre manages its own server rooms, maintaining compliance with the standard and reviewing access will be straightforward. If the servers are provided by a local hosting facility (e.g. the parent university or hospital's IT department) the centre should ensure that it can review the access procedures and access list on a regular basis (e.g. every year, or after a major perceived change in risk).

Even if a centre uses third-party SaaS systems, it is important that it is satisfied that the data is housed in a secure physical environment.

In general the centre will retain overall responsibility for data management, delegated to it by the sponsor, including data security. In this case the centre should demand from their SaaS supplier – who might in turn get the details from their infrastructure provider – the details of physical access control.

Commercial data centres should be compliant with ISO 27001, ISO 22237, SOC 2 or equivalent certifications. Simply quoting the certification of an external hosting organisation is not, however, sufficient – the centre needs to know the details of physical access control.

The servers may be physically distant from the data centre and the control of access may not easily allow escorted auditor entry, so physical inspection of server rooms is not essential in assessing the standard – though it can certainly be insightful if it is possible. More useful would be controlled documents and literature from the data centre and/or the server hosting facility describing the exact location of data, the security measures in use, the access policies applied, the frequency of review and how the results of such reviews are communicated with the unit.

IT01.03: Secured power supply

The power supply to computer infrastructure should be secured, e.g. by an uninterruptible power supply (UPS) unit, to allow an orderly shutdown on power failure.

Servers and related equipment need to be protected from loss of power, at least to the extent that they can be shut down in an orderly fashion. The uninterruptible power supplies and any other equipment used for this purpose should also be tested

periodically (according to the manufacturer's recommendations) to ensure that they are functioning correctly.

Evidence that this was the case would come from controlled documents, from a local or external hosting facility, describing the UPS and other power security measures, records of testing of the UPS or at least a description of the testing regime, and any records of and discussions about incidents when the UPS became necessary. Many UPS systems generate their own logs to document tests and power failures, and these can be a useful source of evidence. Physical inspection of the server rooms may not be possible, and is not essential in assessing the standard.

If the centre manages its own server rooms then it is easy for the centre to provide the evidence described above. If the servers are provided by a local or external hosting facility (e.g. the parent university or hospital's IT department) the centre should assure itself that the power supply is secured, and that the mechanisms are tested, by obtaining the relevant information or logs from the hosting facility. Even if a centre uses SaaS, it is important that it is satisfied that the physical servers being used are protected from power loss in this way – by asking their SaaS supplier for confirmation that this is the case and for the supporting evidence, e.g. contract or SLA. For commercial centres, compliance ISO 22237 or equivalent would be expected.

UPS systems are usually designed only to last long enough for a managed shutdown. Though not a requirement of ECRIN standards, it is, therefore, good practice to have an alternative power supply, e.g. from a local generator, available to allow continued functioning during a lengthy power loss.

IT01.04 Controlled environment

Computer infrastructure should be housed in a controlled environment.

Servers require controlled conditions of temperature and humidity for optimum functioning and any server room should at least be able to maintain temperatures within a defined range.

If the centre manages its own server rooms then it should be straightforward for the centre to provide the evidence for this, either by direct demonstration and/or reference to the specification of the server room and temperature and other environmental records. If the servers are provided by a local or external hosting facility (e.g. parent university or hospital's IT department) the centre should assure itself that temperature is properly controlled by obtaining the relevant details from the hosting facility. Even if a centre uses SaaS, it is important that it is satisfied that the physical servers being used are being managed in an appropriate environment –

by asking their SaaS supplier for confirmation that this is the case and for the supporting evidence.

Most commercial hosting facilities go well beyond temperature control and have full HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) control systems installed, and compliance with ISO 22237 or similar would be expected.

IT01.05: Fire and smoke alarms

Rooms used to house computer infrastructure should be fitted with heat and smoke alarms, monitored 24/7, and tested regularly.

Servers and related equipment must be protected from fire. Although heat and smoke alarms are commonplace, the key requirement here is that they are monitored continuously (the monitoring may be off-site), and tested periodically.

If the centre manages its own server rooms then the centre can provide evidence by direct demonstration and/or reference to the specification of the server room and test records, etc. If the servers are provided by a local or external hosting facility it should still assure itself that an adequate fire alarm system is in place by obtaining the relevant details from the hosting facility. Even if a centre uses SaaS, it is important that it is satisfied that the servers used have fire protection – by asking their SaaS supplier for confirmation that this is the case and for the supporting evidence. For commercial centres, compliance with ISO 22237 or equivalent would be expected.

IT01.06: System failure and response

Failure of any computer infrastructure directly supporting clinical trial activity should result in alerts being sent automatically to relevant personnel.

If key computer infrastructure experiences some sort of failure it is important that staff are aware of this in a timely way. The timing of notifications, and subsequent response, should be based on the potential service impact, particularly with respect to patient safety and data integrity, and aligned with RPO/RTO expectations (see IT04.01). For critical systems notifications should be immediate, or at least during normal local business hours.

Note that this standard covers all equipment ‘directly supporting clinical trial activity’, i.e. it excludes machines used exclusively for test and development, but includes all production machines and those used for immediate backup, e.g. mirrored or failover machines. Failure of a production machine is often obvious because the functionality suddenly disappears, but the centre also needs to be aware of ‘silent failures’ that may occur in a backup machine, and which may not become obvious until later – perhaps when that functionality is urgently required.

‘Relevant personnel’ means those who need to react to the failure and start any recovery or failover process. For externally hosted facilities the relevant staff would, therefore, normally be within those facilities. But, wherever located, the staff initially contacted should then normally inform the staff who need to liaise with end users, or send messages directly to end users themselves. In the event of a lengthy system failure they would then need to provide periodic updates on progress.

Evidence that the standard has been met could come from inspecting the server monitoring system(s) (or at least descriptions of those systems, in the case of an external hosting facility), looking at examples of any past alerts, and interviewing staff.

In some situations, when supporting sites in a different time zone, it may be necessary to extend the hours covered by these arrangements, so that problems can be responded to and resolved quickly within the business hours of the sites. This may involve centre staff being ‘on call’ or even working additional hours, but such arrangements will be dependent on appropriate resourcing. The sponsor would, therefore, need to make the final decision on the time span to be covered in the context of any particular trial, and make funds available as needed.

Providing automatic 24/7 server monitoring, with alerts being sent immediately to relevant personnel, allows failures to be picked up quickly in the evenings, over weekends and national holidays. It is a service that is often available from commercial hosting providers and another reason to consider using such a service.

The inclusion of software monitoring, in addition to the hardware monitoring provided by server monitoring systems, is also seen as good practice and use of such systems is encouraged. This can include success/fail messaging built into scheduled jobs, e.g. backup completion, automated overnight data transfers.

A response to cyber-attack should be considered and included in the BCP/DR documentation (see IT04 below). This should include an awareness of risks, mitigation, and rapid response, perhaps supported by the wider organisation.

IT01.07: Server support and recovery from downtime

Hardware support arrangements should be in place to allow equipment to be replaced or repaired following the centre’s own planned times for disaster recovery.

Centres or their host IT organisation should have a maintenance agreement in place, usually with the original hardware suppliers, to allow for the prompt repair or replacement of critical equipment like servers. Use of virtual machines may improve resilience, but it is still important that failure of supporting hardware is dealt with promptly to minimise risk of downtime.

For centres using external IT infrastructure this requirement will normally be taken care of by the hosting organisation, and will normally be transparent to the data centre itself. As usual, even though a centre may not be directly involved in managing support arrangements, it still needs to satisfy itself that those arrangements are in place and that they meet the centre's requirements for service continuity, and it should be able to justify that judgement. Centres using SaaS systems would also need to be satisfied that their SaaS suppliers had similar arrangements in place with their infrastructure providers.

Continuity planning and response to issues should be proportionate to potential impact, e.g. hardware supporting 24-hour randomisation system, vs server used to test new software.

Evidence that the standard has been reached include the documents and/or agreements (e.g. SLAs) that detail how repairs and replacements are managed so that specified response and recovery times (RPO/RTO) can be achieved for the various systems used by the centre. These should form part of the Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery Plans (see IT04.01).

IT01.08: Server configuration records

Detailed records of server configurations must be available, allowing accurate rebuild.

The current configuration (operating system version and settings, applications, users, utilities, etc.) of each server directly supporting clinical trials activity should be stored. This allows a machine to be accurately rebuilt to the same state if necessary, and also permits further work on a server to be carried out safely, based on full knowledge of the machine's existing state.

For centres using external IT infrastructure (including the institution's central IT department) this requirement will normally be taken care of by processes internal to the host infrastructure, and be transparent to the data centre itself. Taking and storing machine snapshots, nightly and/or before application of patches, is a common mechanism for doing this. In such cases the centre would not normally see the day-to-day records of configuration management, but it still needs to satisfy itself that effective processes are in place to provide such management, and be able to justify that judgement. For centres directly controlling their own machine configurations, server monitoring systems may allow configuration information to be updated automatically. In others, regular or ad hoc 'snapshots' of server configurations may be taken.

If snapshots are taken infrequently, e.g. at initial build and before and after major changes, that is acceptable as long as there are accurate records of any updates and patches that are applied between those snapshots. All updates should, therefore, be

logged and, along with the configuration snapshot information, the log should always be available (the update log that Windows automatically maintains on a server is not sufficient, because the times that a server becomes inaccessible is exactly when the details are most likely to be needed). The evidence required to show this standard has been met would normally be:

- controlled documents or documents from a hosting organisation detailing how server configuration information is maintained and by whom; and
- for locally controlled servers, up-to-date configuration records and patch logs for the servers concerned.

IT01.09: Server software maintenance

Necessary software updates should be identified and applied in a timely but safe manner to server operating systems, utilities and applications.

This standard requires that there is active management of server patching and upgrades, i.e. a set of procedures that determine how this is done, when, and by whom. Though there can be a risk in not applying patches as these often close security loopholes, there is also an inherent risk in adding a patch or update to a functioning system. Patch management should include safeguards to try to minimise these risks.

In this standard, ‘utilities’ mean things like programs to support anti-malware systems, remote access and backups, while ‘applications’ include (but are certainly not limited to) databases and clinical data management systems. The standard effectively applies to all software installed on servers directly supporting clinical trial activities.

Responsibilities for patching can be complex, but must be understood by all parties or there is a danger that some updates will ‘fall through the gaps’ and not occur at all. In many cases, patches to the underlying operating systems and utilities will be managed by the organisation hosting the IT infrastructure, while updating applications will be the responsibility of the data centre, but the situation will vary considerably between centres.

Patch testing for operating systems and common applications may be carried out by specialist commercial patch testing services. Using such a service reduces risk, but does not eliminate it so patch management should still include defensive mechanisms (e.g. taking data backups and configuration snapshots) so that the patch can be rolled back and the system restored quickly to its former state if necessary. Patches and upgrades to less generic programs, like a CDMS, or a statistics package, will often need additional management, e.g. application to a test server and evaluation or revalidation by staff before application to a production

server. Like all change management practices, management of patches and upgrades should be based upon a risk assessment – with the options including making the change, delaying the change, or not making it at all.

The data centre should be aware of when and how all patches and updates are applied, including those for which it is not directly responsible. It will often need to be involved in patches carried out by the parent or hosting organisation, partly to help warn users of any interruptions to services and minimise disruption, partly because only data centre staff are likely to have the expertise to test specialist systems after patches have been applied.

Where software cannot be updated, the risk should be mitigated as far as possible. For example, an expensive piece of lab equipment might connect to a computer running a defunct version of Windows. The cost of replacing the equipment might be unjustifiable. Mitigation might include removing the computer from the network, or removing internet access. Any such situations should be recorded on a risk register, with mitigation and justifications.

Evidence that the standard has been met would include:

- controlled documents, and/or documentation from IT infrastructure hosts, detailing how risks associated with patches/updates are assessed, and how any changes are made, as safely as possible;
- specific patch/upgrade records that demonstrate that the patches identified as required, in the context of risk assessment, have been applied;
- risk register justifying any unsupported software with mitigation; and
- a discussion with the relevant staff about how the system works in practice.

IT02: Logical Security

The standards in this section cover protecting data from unauthorised access, from outside the data centre (controlling and differentiating access from within the centre is dealt with in IT03).

Variations between systems and the constantly changing nature of security threats mean that it is difficult to stipulate specific security measures for systems. What is essential, however, is an ongoing review of security risks, security mechanisms and incidents (hence IT02.01) as well as general commitment to the principles of data protection and access control (as illustrated by the other standards in the section).

IT02.01: Security management system

Regular reviews of security (practices, incident analysis, risk assessment, documentation etc.) should occur across all IT systems relevant to clinical trials activity, followed by any necessary corrective and preventative actions.

This standard is equivalent to implementing a basic Information Security Management System (ISMS), ensuring that security measures are not specified and implemented as a one-off activity, but are periodically reviewed in the context of changing threats and risks. Reviews will necessarily include management and budgetary issues as well as technical discussions, and should, therefore, inform and/or involve senior management. The term is borrowed from the ISO 27001 standard on Information Security Management [10], though there is no expectation that the centre or its parent organisation has obtained or is seeking full ISO 27001 certification.

The essential features of an ISMS are:

- Identification of security risks, together with an assessment of the potential damage to the centre from a failure in each case.
- Selection and implementation of security controls to reduce the identified risks and to meet the security objectives.
- Continued review and adjustment of security controls as circumstances change and incidents occur and are analysed.

One would expect an external hosting facility to be able to describe/demonstrate such a review mechanism for IT security – indeed many will have ISO 27001 certification. Many universities and university hospitals operate security review groups at the institution level, which is fine as long as the data centre has some means of participating in or accessing that group. Data centres using their own on-

premise infrastructure will need to develop and demonstrate a security management system themselves.

Evidence that this standard has been met would include:

- controlled documents dealing with system security;
- minutes or other records of a periodic review process and any subsequent corrective or preventative action;
- records of incident analysis and any subsequent corrective or preventative action; and
- interviews with staff to discuss how the system operates in practice.

IT02.02: Commitment to data protection

The centre and its staff can demonstrate compliance with and commitment to all relevant data protection legislation, including the provision of related training programmes.

A key component of system security relates to data protection legislation and policies.

Here ‘relevant data protection legislation’ means that which applies in the countries where trials managed by the centre are carried out, not just the legislation of the centre’s own country. For instance, German and Danish data protection regulations would be relevant to a French centre if that centre was running a trial with centres in Germany and Denmark. Note that the introduction of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has reduced, but not removed, differences between countries, because large parts of the regulation dealing with research data have been left to the discretion of national legislatures to implement.

For centres operating outside the European Economic Area (EEA) their host country should have been judged as ‘adequate’ with respect to data protection legislation [17].

Note that processing of data includes storage of backups which might be geographically remote from the live data, and that remote access to data, e.g. via VPN, is also considered to be processing.

The expectation is that staff are made aware of their legal and ethical responsibilities under data protection as part of their initial and continued training (whether carried out by the centre or external agencies). Controlled documents should also be available that demonstrate the centre’s commitment to data protection and how they comply with relevant legislation.

A member of staff, usually within the parent organisation rather than the data centre itself unless the data centre is a separate legal entity, will be identified as the organisation's Data Protection Officer (DPO), as this is now a mandated requirement under the GDPR for all data controllers and many data processors. That person should be available to provide local support and guidance to data centre staff, and may be involved in providing training input. Given the specialist regulatory requirements surrounding trial data, however, it can also be useful to identify one or more individuals within the data centre who can also develop expertise in this area, liaising with the institution's DPO as necessary.

The evidence required to show that the standard has been met includes:

- controlled documents that describe how the centre implements data protection policies and the responsibilities of members of staff under those policies;
- identification of the institution's Data Protection Officer, plus one or more staff identified within the unit as having special expertise in data protection legislation;
- records of training concerned with data protection (some level of training will be required for all IT/DM staff); and
- interviews with staff to check understanding of data protection requirements and discuss how the systems work in practice.

IT02.03: External firewalls

External firewalls should be in place and tested to demonstrate that they block inappropriate access.

A centre or (more normally) its host IT organisation should have external firewalls set up to block unauthorised access from outside the centre.

Exactly how the firewalls would need to be configured will depend on circumstances. A centre running eRDC, for instance, would normally have externally facing web server(s) placed in the 'demilitarised zone' or DMZ, logically outside the rest of the institution's network. Centres providing non web-based remote access, e.g. through VPN or Citrix, will need to configure their firewalls to support this.

The firewall configurations need testing to check that they are effectively blocking access. But, as testing has to be against a specification, there should also be a clear description of the access allowed/prohibited for each of the major systems.

Routine penetration testing is recommended. Such testing can be done by commercial organisations, but in the non-commercial sector could also be done by

arranging mutual testing between institutions. Pen-testing of internet-facing applications is strongly encouraged. All tests should be documented, including findings and associated CAPA.

It is also good practice to continually monitor traffic activity and to try to identify and investigate any hacking or denial of service attempts.

Evidence for the standard being met would include:

- explanation of how the firewall configuration worked to block inappropriate access;
- records of firewall specifications and related tests that demonstrate effective blocking of access;
- in the case of externally hosted facilities, equivalent documents that demonstrate appropriate external security. This might include certification against appropriate ISO IT security standards; and
- audit certificates or records of penetration tests if applicable.

IT02.04: Encrypted transmission

Clinical data transmitted over the internet to or from the trials unit should be encrypted.

All clinical data must be encrypted if transmitted to and from the centre over the internet to prevent eavesdropping, tampering and ‘man-in-the-middle’ security attacks.

This will normally be in the context of eRDC, when the https protocol is commonly used to encrypt transmitted information. It may also take place in the context of a VPN or Citrix connection. In the latter case the encryption should extend to the whole of the data transmission and not just the initial exchange of machine identities.

An alternative approach is to encrypt the data before it is sent from the site, for instance using an AES algorithm built into the data capture system. In such cases the data is also stored in an encrypted form. This requires careful encryption key management, but the transport mechanism can then be plain http.

Standards for encryption is an evolving area and the centre should ensure they are aware of and using current best practice, e.g. SSL replaced by TLS, TLS 1.2 by 1.3.

Centre staff will need to explain how the systems they use support encryption and provide the documentary evidence as appropriate, perhaps taken from the vendor’s/developer’s specifications of the CDMS.

IT02.05: Server administrator roles

Administrative access on servers should be restricted to specified members of IT staff, and subject to specific access management practices.

Administrator or ‘admin’ level access to the centre’s servers should be restricted to a small number of specified staff, usually IT staff within the centre and/or IT hosting organisation with particular responsibility for server management. More senior staff within either the centre or the host IT organisation should not routinely have admin level access unless they also have specific server management or business continuity roles.

Sharing of admin accounts should be avoided where possible. Use of separate user accounts for admin and ‘normal’ activity is encouraged to reduce the potential for unwanted impacts.

Administrator accounts should normally be subject to specific management practices (though these are not always described in a controlled document), so that the security of the access can be maintained over time. For example, it is often necessary to set up one or more shared admin passwords to allow easy access to servers or specific services outside normal hours. It might then be necessary to change all such passwords after key staff leave, especially if their leaving was not by choice.

From the point of view of business continuity, it may be a good idea to have some key administrative passwords stored off site (traditionally in a sealed envelope in a safe). This can conflict, however, with the need to periodically change these passwords to ensure that they are not compromised. There is no easy answer to this problem, though using a secure cloud-based ‘password locker’ may work in some cases, as long as it is kept up to date.

The evidence that this standard has been met would include:

- the current list of staff with administrative access, or the relevant documentation/description received from any external hosting facility; and
- interviewing staff, to allow them to describe the management of administrator accounts and how this works in practice.

IT02.06: Internal blocks on data access

Inappropriate access to centre data from other users of the IT infrastructure should be blocked.

Most centres are a part of a larger parent organisation, and share that organisation’s IT infrastructure. Similarly, if they use external hosting facilities for some or all of

their data they will be one tenant among many within the hosting facility, sometimes sharing the same servers with other tenants.

In either case there is a need to block access to the centre's data from users from other organisations or departments.

For a university, there is a particular need to block accidental or deliberate attempted access by student users, while for a hospital there is a need to prevent any unauthorised access into hospital systems from the centre, as well as vice versa.

One method used to block access is building internal firewalls between different parts of the network, but other forms of access control (e.g. domain and user group management) may be used instead of or in addition to firewalls.

The evidence that the standard has been met will include:

- relevant controlled documents describing how access is blocked, or equivalent information from external hosting facilities; and
- interviews with staff to confirm how the system works in practice.

IT02.07: Encryption of non-physically secured data

Clinical data relating to individuals should be stored on protected servers and storage devices. It should not be stored on non-secured devices (e.g. on laptops, desktops, USB sticks.) unless encrypted.

This standard says that any non-aggregated data, i.e. data that relates to individual trial participants, must not be stored on non-secured devices unless encrypted. This includes demographic, treatment, and lab details, as well as data relating to clinical signs and symptoms – anything that is an attribute of a single study participant or their experience.

Secured devices are servers and network storage devices that are physically secured by being in locked rooms, and logically secured by being within the centre's (or its IT host organisation's) firewall. Non-secured devices include desktop PCs and laptops as well as USB sticks and CDs/DVDs, which are not encrypted. (Desktop PCs can easily be stolen, and frequently are, even from premises that were believed to be secure.)

Unless there is good reason not to, it is recommended that **all** data be encrypted at rest, regardless of the nature or security of the device. This mitigates the possibility that a disk removed from a server may mistakenly end up in the public domain.

Likewise, the use of mobile devices for storing and transferring individual clinical data is discouraged, even if encrypted; secure file transfer systems are preferred.

Wherever possible, individual clinical data should be accessed using managed rather than personal devices.

Please note: No distinction is made between data that contains obvious patient identifying data (PID) and data which does not. This is because PID is hard to define and the distinction is not absolute. Obvious patient identifying data, like name, initials, and health system number stand at one end of a continuum. At the other extreme is anonymised data without any such details or links to data that might contain them, and without localising data (either in space, such as hospital name, or in time, such as date of birth).

Some individual clinical data without obvious PID is, however, so detailed, or rare, or includes unique combinations of data values, that – especially with some localising data included as well – it can become potentially identifying. Such data stands somewhere between obvious PID and anonymised data. To keep things simple and safe, therefore, the standard requires all data relating to individuals to be encrypted unless it is stored on a secure device.

The level of encryption required follows current best practice, and as a minimum should match recommendations of the relevant national research or health organisation (typically 256-bit AES). Many centres now routinely provide automatic ‘whole-drive’ encryption for laptops and USB sticks, which makes it much easier to demonstrate compliance with the standard. This does mean, however, that staff need to be aware that they should not use their own devices or USB sticks for data – only those that are issued to them by the centre.

Evidence for the standard being met can come from:

- the controlled documents describing the policy;
- direct examination of laptops and desktops; and
- interviews with staff, e.g. to check their understanding of the relevant controlled documents.

IT03: Logical Access

The standards in this section cover the control and differentiation of access from within the centre (protecting data from unauthorised access from outside the data centre is dealt with in IT02).

The access being considered is to the data centre's own network and to 'all systems directly supporting clinical trial activity'. This most obviously includes the CDMS, but will also include (for instance) treatment allocation and trial administration systems. It excludes systems used exclusively for development, testing and training.

IT03.01: Logical access procedures

Controlled documents covering access control to all systems directly supporting clinical trial activity should be in place.

This standard simply requires that controlled documents exist that govern access management, both to the network, which acts as the initial portal, and then to systems involved in directly supporting clinical trial activity. Network access is often managed by the centre's host organisation, while the centre would normally manage access to its own systems. There will, therefore, often be two sets of controlled documents.

The evidence will be the documents themselves, which should include a summary of responsibilities, processes, outcomes and documentation involved in controlling logical access.

IT03.02 Network login management

Secure network log-in management should be enforced on all users.

A robust and secure method of authenticating users should be implemented. Typically this would be through unique user account and strong password, though biometric authentication, e.g. fingerprint or facial recognition, is now common.

Use of a user ID and password may be augmented using multi-factor authentication, often implemented using a mobile application such as Microsoft Authenticator or Duo. Consideration should be given to situations where mobile signals are weak or absent and alternative solutions, such as code-generating 'dongles', considered.

If devices are shared then separate accounts should be used.

Advice on best practice for strong passwords should be provided to users. Currently evidence favours use of three (say) random words rather than enforcing a specific arrangement of upper- and lower-case letters, numbers and symbols – which may be difficult to remember.

Evidence that this standard was met would come from:

- controlled documents detailing the management policies for network log-in;
- a description of the current users group and how their access rights are distributed.
- proformas and other documentation, and/or demonstration showing those policies being used; and
- a discussion with centre staff about how the local network log-in policy worked.

IT03.03: Network lockout

Logins to the network should be locked after a locally determined inactivity period, requiring secured re-activation.

When an employee moves away from their machine while logged into the network and/or a particular system, there is a risk that another user may use that machine, ‘hijack’ their access rights and gain unauthorised entry to systems. There should, therefore, be an automatic mechanism that locks the screen and which requires a password or equivalent mechanism to unlock. The mechanism must be automatic after a pre-set time – not normally more than 15 minutes.

Local security policy should require users to manually lock machines before leaving their desks.

The lock-out should apply to the network log-in and, therefore, lock the whole machine. Many CDMs also provide an automatic log-out mechanism, but this is insufficient on its own.

Evidence for this can be most easily obtained from direct observation, backed up by interviews with staff.

IT03.04: Remote access (via VPN etc, not internet browser)

Remote access should be controlled using the same principles as local access control, and should not normally include access to the host’s network (unless the user has a pre-existing identity on that network).

Remote access is used here to mean direct access to a server and specific applications and/or the centre’s network, e.g. using Citrix or VPN, rather than the browser mediated access of an eRDC system to data entry screens.

It may be provided for centre staff, who will usually have their own identity on the local network (for instance a monitor when working away from the centre) or for

staff who are completely external to the centre, perhaps working for a collaborating organisation.

Remote access management should reflect this. It should prevent external users from gaining access to anything other than the specific applications and datasets that they have been authorised to use, and, in particular, prevent access through to the host's network. Internal employees may, in some systems, enjoy the same access as they would have if they logged in locally (more often a sub-set), and the remote access mechanisms should be able to manage this effectively.

Evidence for this can be obtained from:

- relevant controlled documents;
- from interviews discussing how any remote access is managed; and
- demonstration of the remote access system's access control mechanisms and records, including relevant proformas.

IT03.05: Access control management

All systems that directly support clinical trials activity and that require access controls should have mechanisms, e.g. using roles, group membership, that can be used to effectively differentiate and manage access.

This standard requires that sufficient mechanisms exist to provide differential access, in terms of both allowed functionality and data. This might be by role assignment in a CDMS, or by explicit allocation of rights within a file management system, and would normally be done through managing group membership rather than on an individual basis.

The standard is concerned with all systems 'that require access controls', starting with the initial log-in to the centre's/parent organisation's network for internal staff, but including in particular access to the CDMS for both internal and remote eRDC staff, and any other systems (e.g. treatment allocation, coding, pharmacovigilance) that directly support clinical trials activity. In general, remote site staff should only have access to the data (and related material, like queries) on their own site.

Control of access should also include access to reports, data extraction and other review mechanisms, i.e. users should only see the data that they have a right to see and be able to run the reports that are relevant to their role within the system.

The evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- the controlled documents dealing with access control for centre and site staff, across the different systems; and
- demonstration of the access control system, especially for the CDMS.

IT03.06: Granularity of access

Access control mechanisms should be granular enough to allow compliance with the data centre's own policies on access control.

This standard (together with IT03.05) emphasises the need to support granular access, i.e. to allow fine control over the access provided and the functionality provided with it, to different datasets and for different roles.

Granularity clearly applies to remote eRDC staff, who should only ever see their 'own' site's data, but it also applies within the centre, where staff should not be able to see data or other files that are sensitive scientifically, e.g. randomisation lists, or clinically/commercially, e.g. analysis results, unless they have a genuine need to do so.

Granularity may also be found in fine control over access to clinical data: for example, a member of staff who works on one study should be able to see and edit the data for that study; her manager might be able to view that data, but not edit it; a monitor might be able to raise and close queries for that study, but not enter data, etc.

The granularity required should match the centre's policies on access control, which is driven by the organisation of staff, tasks and systems.

Centres that store more obvious PID (e.g. patient names and addresses used to contact trial subjects in quality-of-life studies) will usually need to provide greater granularity of access to protect that data than centres that do not (or are not allowed to because of local data protection legislation).

Evidence that the standard has been met includes:

- controlled documents detailing how access control is implemented;
- direct demonstration of access control mechanisms and inspection of systems, especially with regard to particularly sensitive data types; and
- a discussion with staff about how and why the necessary granularity is supported.

IT03.07: Administration of access to clinical data

Access rights to systems storing or processing clinical data should be regularly reviewed, changes to access requested and actioned according to defined procedures, with records kept of all rights, when granted, why and by whom.

This standard deals with the administration of access to clinical data systems. It requires that a system is in place to request and implement changes, to record when access rights were changed and by whom and that the rights are reviewed

periodically (at least quarterly) to ensure that they are all still required. This is particularly important in blinded trials where access to unblinding data may be restricted and unwanted access could seriously compromise analysis.

Periodic review is particularly important for remote users, who are often employed by other organisations, and who may, therefore, leave that employment without the data centre being made aware that they can drop access for that user. This could risk data integrity, especially if the leaving was not voluntary. A variety of mechanisms are available to try to reduce the time lag between someone leaving and their access being revoked. None are 100% reliable, but using two or more together can reduce the risk of unauthorised access by ex-staff. These include:

- monitoring of access, to identify staff who have not logged into the system for some time;
- asking monitors and other site visitors to check the access required at each visit;
- regular reminders to site senior staff to let the data centre know of staff changes; and
- coupling any requests for new access at a site with a check on the existing accesses required.

The standard only applies to those systems dealing with clinical data, but it would be good practice to extend the requirement and record all access requests/changes, including to the network and other systems (e.g. trial administration).

Evidence that the standard has been met should come from:

- the relevant controlled documents;
- examples of the request and review procedures; and
- the records maintained within the system itself.

IT04: Business Continuity

Business continuity (BC) is the set of activities performed by an organisation to ensure that critical business functions will remain available to staff, customers, suppliers and regulators, etc., after a major loss of function. The loss may be caused by a natural disaster (flood, fire, earthquake, hurricane, etc.) or be man-made (e.g. sabotage, walkouts) or be as simple as the sudden loss of key staff.

BC is not restricted to IT systems. It can include communicating with clients, storing copies of key material off-site, arranging alternative premises, hiring consultants or temporary staff and finding alternative service suppliers. Disaster recovery (DR) is the process of restoration or continuation of IT systems after a massive loss of functionality.

DR may include rebuilding and/or restoring data for applications, and re-establishing hardware, communications and other IT infrastructure. Key to any disaster recovery policy is the retention of copies of data, but so also is keeping copies of other key information (passwords, activation keys, scheduled jobs, user information, etc).

This section deals with business continuity in general (IT04.01) though the rest of the standards are focused on IT disaster recovery.

IT04.01: Business continuity planning

The centre should maintain a Business Continuity Plan including Disaster Recovery measures in responses to potential disaster scenarios.

This standard requires the centre to document a Business Continuity Plan (BCP) covering a range of disaster scenarios, e.g. cyber-attack, loss of power to local server room, or theft of equipment. Individual scenarios should be assessed for likelihood and impact, and Disaster Recovery (DR) plans which describe the measures to be taken to resolve the issue within an appropriate time frame.

For example, the loss of a hard disk in a RAID array with sufficient redundancy might be a relatively relaxed process with a hardware vendor expected to arrive and swap the failed disk within 24 hours; the response to a fire in a server room might require more immediate action, to notify fire services, replace damaged equipment, etc.

The BCP must include details of data backup and recovery processes, specifically the point to which data can be recovered (Recovery Point Objective, RPO), and how long this recovery is expected to take (Recovery Time Objective, RTO) – see sections below.

The BCP should cover response to cyber-attack, including immediate and follow-up activities. This may be aligned and supported by a wider organisational policy and response team.

The BCP should consider wider (than IT) risks such as loss of key staff members. The usual mechanisms for dealing with this (good documentation of activity, deputising arrangements, job sharing or shadowing, etc.) would not normally need to be part of a BCP in any detail, but references to the relevant personnel or training policies/documents should be included.

The BCP should include telephone contact details for key staff, noting that a potential impact of some disasters might be that digital communication, e.g. via email, is not possible. A hard copy of the BCP should be maintained in multiple locations, including at least one off-site.

Testing of responses to disaster scenarios should take place routinely, and at least annually. These tests might be real or virtual, e.g. physically removing a power lead from a server and monitoring the UPS response, or a 'desktop exercise' to work through a server replacement in the event that a server room suffers a catastrophic fire.

A BCP should be maintained even where centres make use of external IT infrastructure. In such cases the external provider should be expected to maintain its own BCP and make response times clear in its SLA or contract with the centre. The centre's BCP may reference the provider's BCP, but it must satisfy itself that arrangements meet the centre's requirements for service continuity, and should be able to justify this. Centres using SaaS systems would also need to be satisfied that their SaaS suppliers have similar arrangements in place with their infrastructure providers.

The BCP should be considered a dynamic document and routinely updated, at least annually or in light of system or service changes, and approved by senior management. It is crucial that risks to business-critical systems, and the resource provided or expected to secure and maintain these, is clearly understood and approved by the leadership team.

The evidence required is the BCP document itself, evidence of regular review, and of DR testing.

IT04.02: Backup policies

Policies for data backup and restore should match the centre's requirements, and the details of the procedures should be available to the centre.

Policies should describe details of data backup and recovery processes, noting RPO and RTO, which should reflect business criticality of data, and resource available to protect this.

Backups of relatively static file-based data might be executed each night, though more frequent backups may be desirable for dynamic systems such as a CDMS. The RPO/RTO for each system should be made clear. For example, the tolerable downtime for a 24/7/365 randomisation system is likely to be much lower than that for a long-term data archive. The BCP should note RPO and RTO for all key systems.

Consideration should also be given to the granularity of backup and its impact on recovery capabilities. Traditional file backups provide access to restore individual files, and database systems such as SQL server support transactional backups that allow restoration to specific timepoints (if implemented). Default backups in modern commercial data centres may rely on snapshots of entire virtual servers. This may expedite restoration of a whole server, but may complicate that of individual files or databases. For example, in order to restore a single database, one might have to restore the entire server snapshot to a new virtual machine, extract the specific database, transfer this to the production machine, and then import it. Such complexities are one of the reasons why practical testing is essential.

Encryption of backups is strongly advocated and provides resilience against cyber-attack.

Additional issues to be considered might include:

- the length of time a backup should be retained (or equivalently, from how far back should it be possible to retrieve data?)
- how much monitoring of IT operations (e.g. nightly backup) is required within the centre?
- when should restore operations be tested (see 04.06)?

These questions have sometimes been seen as technical ‘IT’ issues, but in fact they are critical operational issues and need to be documented, considered and approved by the centre’s senior management.

As noted in IT04.01, backup policy should be considered as part of wider BCP, not regarded as just an IT issue. The reality of the impact – and likely downtime – when recovering from a major system failure should not come as a surprise to senior management.

Where third-party data centres are used, either provided by a central IT department in a university or hospital, system vendor, or a completely independent commercial hosting facility, it is crucial that the service provided is clearly understood so the centre can judge whether it is acceptable.

The centre's requirements should be included within contract or SLA. External hosts who cannot provide the necessary flexibility of provision should be avoided.

The evidence would be the controlled and/or contractual documents, plus a discussion with centre staff (and if available staff from the external hosting facility) to explore how the arrangements work in practice.

IT04.03: Backup frequency

Backups must be taken using a managed, documented and automatic regime that ensures new or changed data is backed up within 24 hours, and which allows the centre to check that the system is operating properly.

As noted in IT04.02, backup frequency should reflect business need, though this should not normally be less than every 24 hours. This may be achieved through a 'full' backup, i.e. all current data, or just the data which has been created or changed since a previous full backup. It is normal to execute a full backup at regular intervals so as to reset the baseline for restorations. Daily backups should be regarded as a minimum, and more frequent backups implemented where possible and justified by the BCP.

If a centre is managing its own data backups it is relatively straightforward to monitor that the process is operating properly.

If backups are the responsibility of an IT host organisation the centre still needs to assure itself (e.g. by receiving regular reports/copies of logs) that the backup process is operating properly. In such cases the centre should take a risk-based decision on what level of monitoring is acceptable, given their knowledge of hosting organisation systems and contractual agreements that are in place. External hosts that are unwilling to provide monitoring data or access should be avoided.

In practice there may be several different backup regimes, for instance one that applies to files on a SAN and another that applies to databases on a dedicated server. There may also be mechanisms for taking snapshots of virtual machines as well as (or instead of) conventional file-based backup. The centre may, therefore, need to develop separate documents/monitoring regimes for each.

The evidence that the standard has been met includes:

- documentation describing the backup regime and how it is managed, either from the data centre or the IT host organisation; and
- logs of the backup process and/or periodic summary reports indicating the backups are proceeding as required.

IT04.04: Backup storage

Backup media storage (location, protection, redundancy) should be sufficient to avoid data loss if there is a fire, cyber-attack or other disaster.

Simply backing up data does not guarantee that it will survive a large-scale disaster such as a fire or cyber-attack, especially if it remains in the same location as the original data.

A variety of mechanisms exist to ensure that a such a disaster will not wipe out data, for instance secured off-site storage of tapes, on-site storage in fireproof safes, duplication of backup data to a mirrored site, and twinned, but physically separate backup systems (e.g. at opposite ends of a large university or hospital campus).

This standard requires that one of these mechanisms, or something equally effective, is in place to ensure that if a large-scale disaster happens at one of the data storage sites a copy of the data is still available. On-site storage of tapes in fireproof safes is a traditional approach, but is rarely adequate – it usually only preserves infrequent copies and needs manual intervention. Given the low cost of electronic storage, better alternatives are generally available.

Centres using external hosts should assure themselves of the specific level of resilience and recovery provided. This should be clearly stated in the contract/SLA and response to failure included in the BCP/DR plan.

Consideration should always be given to potential impacts on patient safety and data integrity when choosing backup services.

The evidence that the standard was being met would come from:

- controlled documents describing the procedures for storage of backups and the systems supporting this; and
- a discussion with staff to clarify procedures and explore how the systems work in practice.

IT04.05: Backup – environment

Any necessary data management/administration data (access groups, log-ins, scheduled jobs, etc.) should be backed up and restorable.

Though the retention of copies of data is necessary for disaster recovery, so also is keeping copies of other critical information (passwords, activation keys, scheduled jobs, user information, etc.).

This is particularly important for database systems, where the database server may hold a great deal of data management/administration information. This may or may not be backed up automatically by the IT host organisation's systems, and so may

require additional agreements or scripts being run by centre staff. The same sort of data is also necessary for file-based systems, but this is usually backed up along with all the other file material.

The much greater use of virtual machines, and the practice of taking regular 'snapshots' of these machines, reapplying them to hardware when necessary, is making this standard easier to meet for most centres, especially when using external infrastructure rather than on-site servers.

Nevertheless, it is necessary for the centre to be clear about the regime that is being implemented (see IT04.02, IT04.03) and what components of the environment backup process, if any, remain the responsibility of centre staff, for instance by writing and running scripts.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- relevant controlled documents and/or details of procedures within external hosts; and
- interviews with staff, including explanations and demonstration of the backup/restore mechanisms used.

IT04.06: Recovery testing

Testing of restore or failover procedures should take place and be documented, at a frequency that reflects system and staff changes (for all systems relevant to clinical trial activity).

Backup is of little use without corresponding mechanisms for restoring data, and those restore mechanisms must be tested. Details of the backup approach and associated recovery (RPO/RT0) should be documented in the BCP.

Consideration should be given to the practicalities of restoration, whether this be an individual file, specific database or entire server, and whether this activity is carried out on-site or remotely (e.g. commercial data centre), and also recreation of associated permission sets.

The tasks of the data centre include:

- Identifying the possible restore operations that might be required, at the level of files, databases and entire servers.
- Testing these operations or – for external hosts – ensuring that the relevant restore processes are being tested.
- Documenting the test restore exercises (or receiving relevant documents from external hosts).
- Identifying and correcting any problems.

- Repeating test restores, either routinely or after major changes in the server configuration or backup regime or (for restore mechanisms that are the responsibility of the data centre's own staff) when there are changes to the staff.

Even when an external host organisation does most of the work of restoring files or systems, the data centre staff should still be clear about their own role in any restore process, for example, knowing the information that needs to be transmitted to the hosting facility, or any information that needs to be given to end users.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from the documented restore requirements of the centre, and the records of test restores, together with a discussion with centre staff about how restore mechanisms are reviewed and repeated.

IT05: General System Validation

As used within ECRIN standards and related material, ‘validation’ refers to the process of ensuring and documenting that a system or process is functioning as required. In other words, it should indicate whether or not a system or process can be relied upon to be ‘fit for purpose’. This echoes the FDA definition of validation, which is: “Establishing documented evidence that provides a high degree of assurance that a specific process will consistently produce a product meeting its pre-determined specifications and quality attributes.” [11]

This section looks at validation in general, of all systems used by the data centre. There are additional specific aspects of validating trial-specific database systems (CDMAs), but these are covered in section DM01.

The standards in this section are designed to support a flexible approach to validation, one which stresses the underlying principles of validation more than any particular framework or methodology. Those principles are listed below, together with an indication of the standards which support them.

- Planned and documented validation of systems can represent a major investment in time and resources, especially for a small academic trials unit. It is important that the processes, implications and costs of validation are understood at all levels of the centre, but especially by senior management. An overall validation policy needs to be endorsed by senior management, as indicated by approval of the relevant controlled documents (IT05.01).
- Validation of every system or process in detail would be challenging, and maybe unnecessary. Resources must be focused on those systems where the impact of error or malfunction would be greatest and/or the likelihood of errors occurring is highest, with respect to patient safety and data integrity. The key to designing a validation regime is, therefore, risk assessment. A risk assessment methodology should be applied systematically to identify the systems that need to be validated and the level and type of validation required (IT05.02).
- Even if a system or process is not in the direct control of the data centre (for instance is a software service, or a hardware installation hosted externally) the centre still has a responsibility to ensure that the system has been validated. In other words, centres will need to obtain evidence of validation from the relevant external hosts and service suppliers, and should have that evidence available for inspection by external agencies (IT05.02).
- Validation should occur when a system is first introduced into a centre, but systems change, are patched and upgraded, etc., and both the staff and the context, and thus the requirements on the system, can also change.

Validation is, therefore, an ongoing process and centres should have a mechanism to review risk assessment and possible revalidation on a periodic basis as well as during planned change. This applies especially to externally hosted services, where change may take place outside the centre's control – though they should be made aware. Centres need a mechanism to assure themselves that the validation status of external services is retained over time (IT05.03).

- Validation of any particular system needs to be planned and then recorded, in detail, to provide the evidence for subsequent decisions. The complexity of systems and their usage means that absolute validation, i.e. of all possible inputs and situations, may be impossible. Detailed testing should be sufficient, however, to give a 'high degree of assurance' that the system functions as it should, and that it can be relied upon to function as expected under normal demands. In practice, system validation is often done in stages – IQ, OQ and PQ: installation, operational and performance qualification respectively (IT05.04).
- At the end of validation, decisions need to be taken, signed and recorded, as part of the centre's overall quality control mechanism. Verification of function normally provides the basis of the decision to accept, maintain or reject a system for production use, but there is not always a simple link between it and validation. Verifying that a system performs as specified: 'does this system work as advertised?' is different from the acceptance decision: 'does this system work well enough for us to use it?'. The second question demands a risk-based decision based on the answers to the first (IT05.05).
- The need to take decisions about systems highlights one of the great values of validation. It is not just about testing a system's functionality. It also allows a subgroup of staff, normally those who will be the system's main users, to fully understand that system and its relative strengths and weaknesses, and to develop expertise in operating the system. Even though full operational qualification of a system can take some time, this is often an essential first step when introducing a new system to a centre.
- Planned change within systems should be governed by policies that stipulate how those changes should be managed, and the responsibilities and workflows involved. In particular, the policies should require a risk assessment of the impact of the change (IT05.06). The risk assessment and any subsequent revalidation plan, together with the results of that revalidation and the resulting decision, should all be recorded. (IT05.07).
- In a busy data centre it is easy for additional system components to be introduced without being validated. This applies particularly to data reports and extractions, which are often added on an ad hoc basis throughout the

lifetime of systems. Again a risk-based approach should be used to validate, as and when necessary, these data outputs (IT05.08, IT05.09).

- The sponsor is ultimately responsible for ensuring adequate validation activity and should be aware of, and comfortable with the data centre's validation approach. This might be evidenced through discussions at routine meetings, e.g. of introduction of new systems, major changes to existing systems.

IT05.01: Validation policies

Controlled documents should be in place covering system validation approaches, responsibilities and processes.

This standard requires the centre to have developed controlled documents that describe a validation strategy. Typically, this description would include:

- the general principles and approach(es) taken towards validation
- the scope of validation, i.e. the types of systems considered (but not the individual systems, see IT05.02)
- the method(s) used for risk assessment (see IT05.02)
- who should do what, in term of the roles within the centre
- the overall workflow of validation processes
- the expected outputs
- the quality control and sign-offs within the process.

The document will often include reference to particular frameworks and models for validation and risk assessment (e.g. GAMP, PIC/S), but they should not include detailed descriptions or discussions of those frameworks: five pages summarising GAMP 5 does not constitute a validation policy!

Similarly, there is no requirement for any particular framework to be used – partly because those frameworks are themselves evolving, partly because most have their origins in the pharmaceutical industry, and often in manufacturing and laboratory practice rather than the specific validation requirements of data management systems. Existing frameworks can certainly be very useful, but they work better as a starting point for developing local ideas and systems rather than being ‘dropped in’ as complete, fully formed solutions.

The scope of validation should normally include **all the types of system used by the centre to directly support clinical trials**. These include EDC/CDMS, eTMF, ePRO, randomisation systems, etc., seen as directly supporting clinical trial activity.

While the scope of validation includes all systems supporting trials, the magnitude of validation effort should be risk-proportionate based on potential risks to patient

safety and data integrity. For example, a commercial database software application such as Microsoft SQL Server, configured in a typical way, might be deemed a very much lower risk compared to a bespoke software solution used to randomise patients to receive escalating doses of a novel drug.

Systems hosted outside the centre, by parent institution, system vendor, or commercial hosting facility used by the vendor, will normally have been validated by someone else. Despite this these systems remain in scope for validation, but the nature of the evidence will change. Typically the centre will need to perform some degree of due diligence on the vendor, reviewing their validation approach and documentation, in order to satisfy themselves. Evidence of the vendor assessment should be recorded and retained as part of the local validation documentation (see IT05.02).

In summary, this standard is about the centre showing it is clear about its overall approach to validation, and that the approach has been endorsed by management. It is not concerned with individual systems and their validation, which is addressed by IT05.02. The evidence would be the relevant controlled documents.

IT05.02: Validation system inventory

The centre should have an inventory of all the IT systems in scope for validation, the risks associated with each, and, in summary, the validation strategy for each.

Given the decision about the types of systems in scope for validation (see IT05.01) the logical next step is to list each of those systems and carry out a risk assessment for each. That in turn allows the level and type of validation required to be described explicitly.

This list may form a single document (when it is often known as a ‘Validation Master Plan’) or it may be distributed across several documents. The standard only requires that this ‘inventory’ exists within the centre, where it can be used to direct validation activity.

NB ‘Systems’ can include processes that may not be associated with a specialist software package, but which are associated with specific tasks within the centre. This could include, for instance, data transfer between externally and internally hosted infrastructure, or data extraction and processing to support query management. Such processes may use standard operating system features or standard office or statistical software, but the context in which they are used means they can represent a distinct ‘system’ as far as the centre as concerned.

The documentation should identify the risks associated with each system and thus the types and level of testing required. It may also indicate who will be involved, when, and what tools they will use, and the nature of the outputs of the validation

process. Usually only a paragraph or two is needed for each listed system – the key requirement is that a risk assessment has been carried out and the validation requirements have been identified.

One of the key factors determining risk is the software type. A classification scheme in common use (from GAMP 5, [12]) divides software systems into four types (NB Type 2 ‘firmware’ is deprecated), in increasing order of risk:

- 1 – Infrastructure software including operating systems, database managers, etc.
- 3 – Non configurable software including commercial off the shelf software.
- 4 – Configured software, including CDMS, treatment allocation systems.
- 5 – Bespoke software

Although this classification is often used to allocate different validation regimes to systems, it is a very blunt instrument, and many other factors need to be considered. Some of these are listed below.

- The potential impact of malfunction: A component that may impact patient safety, data integrity, or GCP or other regulatory compliance, clearly carries higher potential risk – on patients, the scientific conduct of the trial and the reputation of the data centre – if it operates incorrectly, than (for instance) a module that allows users to easily reset their own passwords or a report that gives a breakdown of accrual figures by site/month.
- The possibility of silent failure: Some problems in systems are obvious as soon as they appear – they will disrupt work, but are unlikely to be allowed to impact the study’s results in the longer term because they will be resolved. Other problems are less obvious and may introduce errors without users being aware of the problem until much later. The costs of resolving the problem, and the potential impact of the issue, are correspondingly greater.
- The numbers of other users: Though systems should always be validated in their own local environment, systems developed by established vendors and in common usage will normally carry less risk than specialist, often locally configured systems. Systems with a large user base are usually extensively tested by their vendors, and there will also be a user community that can identify and publicise potential issues.
- The resources used to develop the system: Systems that are developed by companies with extensive development resources, and well-established quality management practices themselves, are likely to carry less risk than systems created by new and/or small development teams, and especially by a very small in-house development team. (On the other hand, the

responsiveness of the development team in fixing identified problems often varies in the opposite direction.)

External systems, like a SaaS CDMS hosted by the system vendor or a web-based treatment allocation system, may not be within the direct control of the data centre or directly accessible for testing. Nevertheless, the centre still has a responsibility to ensure that these systems have been validated and are fit for purpose.

Evidence of validation will need to be obtained from the external hosts and/or service suppliers, acting almost as a quality inspector for its own suppliers. That evidence should then be made available for inspection as necessary by external agencies, usually with prior agreement of the system suppliers and, if necessary, with confidentiality agreements in place. Service suppliers who cannot or will not provide such proof of validation should not be used. The approach taken should be summarised within the validation system inventory.

An incremental log of reported issues is particularly useful in maintaining an ongoing view of validation status. Such issues might be grouped into ‘bugs’ (functionality that does not behave as specified), user-errors (misuse or misunderstanding), environmental problems (loss of power, cyber-attack) etc. Over time, such a list should provide evidence as to whether the current approach to validation is acceptable. For example, if numerous issues are recorded relating to software bugs with an EDC system, this might indicate a need to increase testing efforts; an absence – or tolerably low level – of such bugs might suggest that current efforts are adequate.

Evidence that this standard has been met would largely be the validation system inventory itself, as well as a discussion with centre staff explaining how risk assessment was applied in practice.

IT05.03: Periodic review of validation

The centre should have mechanisms in place for periodic reviews of the risks associated with systems, with possible subsequent revalidations.

Validation almost always occurs when a system is first introduced into a centre, but systems change, are patched and upgraded, and the context, and thus the requirements of the system, will also change. Centres should, therefore, have a mechanism to review risk assessment and possible revalidation on a periodic basis – over and above the risk assessment that takes place within managed system change. Revalidation will often not be required for the whole of a system, but only for those components perceived to be affected by changes and will, therefore, need to be retested. Validation reviews should consider evidence from recorded issues (see the

recommendation to maintain a log of such issues in 05.02 above) when deciding if current approaches to validation are proportionate.

It is worth stressing that in this context a 'system' or 'process' will normally involve hardware, software and people, and often supporting sub-systems and workflows. For example, a system may be valid with expert users, but not fit for purpose if the users are novices. Even though most system changes will trigger a risk assessment (see IT05.06), this is not necessarily true of organisational and contextual change – hence the need for periodic review of the 'whole system'.

At some point a review may indicate that there is less risk involved in retiring and/or replacing a system than trying to continue to use it. Validation is, therefore, an ongoing process that should last for, and ultimately govern, the lifetime of the system.

The need for ongoing reviews applies particularly to externally hosted services. It is crucial that changes to systems are not made without the data centre's knowledge. There should be clear mechanisms to ensure that – excepting perhaps urgent security hotfixes – there is a sufficient notification period before any changes are rolled-out to users. The notification should provide details of the changes made, likely impact, and be accompanied by evidence of vendor validation activity (e.g. risk assessment, test evidence). Ideally the notification period would include or be preceded by availability of a sandbox environment, provided for local installation or through a separate online environment, to allow any new or updated functionality to be explored. Vendors that do not provide sufficient notification of, or information on software updates should be avoided.

The system inventory or Validation Master Plan (see IT05.02) can provide a good place to record the dates of validation exercises for each system (just the dates and perhaps a summary of the scope and result of the validation), and so provide good evidence for this standard. Other evidence for the standard would come from supporting statements within controlled documentation and a discussion with staff about how the review was implemented, together with related records.

Evidence should also be available to demonstrate adequate sponsor oversight of validation policy and activity. This might be through minutes of routine meetings (perhaps with a standard 'validation issues' prompt) or approval of validation summary review documents.

IT05.04: Validation – detailed evidence

Detailed validation documents should exist for each system, describing the validation carried out, including any test data and protocols, and the results obtained.

Each validation exercise should generate a set of retained detailed validation evidence – i.e. the descriptions of the tests and their results. The documents should also indicate who carried out the tests and when, and may be in electronic or paper format.

It is impossible to test every possible set of inputs into a system, so judgements need to be made on the level of evidence required to show, with ‘a high degree of assurance’, that any particular system component is functioning properly. Again, those judgements should be risk-based with more effort being made to test those parts of systems with greatest potential impact on patient safety or data integrity.

GAMP 5 offers an approach to validation and associated terminology. The recent second edition [20] supports an updated approach, focused less on prescriptive adherence to the V-model [13] and traditional IQ (Installation Qualification), OQ (Operational Qualification) and PQ (Performance Qualification), but rather using these as tools to be deployed where relevant.

The key principle is that there should be a documented specification from which a system may be comprehensively tested. The testing should be nuanced, with more effort directed towards functionality with potential to impact patient safety and data integrity – critical thinking is favoured over a ‘one-size-fits-all’ approach.

The nature of the system should determine the specific approach taken.

Software development requires specification, validation plan, and evidence of testing, including clear traceability linking specification requirements to specific tests. This is the traditional OQ to demonstrate that the requirements in the specification have been met, and often requires a great deal of effort.

Software must then be installed and tested on a specific environment (web servers, databases, etc.) and tested to ensure it is working as expected – the IQ.

The PQ traditionally covers ‘real life’ use and is likely to take place on different environment to that used for OQ, and potentially other users. This might include testing with a typical clinical trial protocol, or with a number of simultaneous users – whatever is needed to demonstrate the software works as needed for the specific use case.

Where the centre develops software locally, all three qualifications must be performed, and documented. For SaaS offerings, it would be expected that the centre carries out a vendor assessment to provide assurance of the vendor’s validation approach and evidence (OQ and IQ). Depending on the outcome of this, there may be a need to perform further local testing (PQ). The latter might be considered to be covered by trial-specific testing (see DM02).

The approach described above comfortably supported the traditional ‘waterfall’ software development model, where a complete specification is prepared and approved *before* development starts. The increasingly common use of agile development instead acknowledges that requirements develop over time, and that it is often better to deliver something quickly – the so-called ‘minimum viable product’ – than wait a long time for a complete system for which the requirements may already have changed.

Supporting validation evidence when following an agile approach is challenging, but can be rewarding. Traditionally a specification was a static document, but it can be supported within a software development system such as Git, Azure DevOps, etc., as a series of hierarchical units (‘epics’, ‘user stories’, ‘features’, etc.). Each item should describe a specific piece of functionality, including success criteria. Further, some degree of testing may be built into the development/deployment process, e.g. automated unit and integration testing. Such automation can greatly reduce the time needed to test releases, while increasing quality (e.g. a new version cannot be deployed unless all tests are successfully passed).

Integrating development and documentation has the advantage that information relating to each functional unit – e.g. specification, testing, traceability, deployment version – can be neatly linked in a way that is much more difficult with traditional documentation (consider the complexity of a traceability matrix for a system of any significance). It is important, however, that such data can be extracted in a coherent and meaningful way, e.g. so as to provide a holistic representation of the system specification at a particular timepoint/version, or to provide test evidence for a specific release. These requirements may be quite challenging to deliver.

The evidence for compliance would be the detailed validation documents themselves, including vendor assessment reports for externally provided systems, for all in-scope systems. *If agile development systems are used, it must be possible to extract coherent equivalent documentation suitable for inspection.*

IT05.05: Validation summaries

A signed and dated summary of the results of each validation should exist.

As well as the detailed results (see IT05.04) any validation exercise should also generate a relatively concise summary of the validation, signed off and dated by one or more key staff, that confirms that validation has been completed and which indicates its result.

A system that failed a validation exercise would normally then have further documents listing the ‘corrective and preventive actions’ (CAPA) to be taken to

remedy the problems identified. A later and more focused revalidation exercise would then confirm that these actions had been successfully carried out.

The 'result' of validation is not always a simple pass/fail. Often it is about whether the system can go into (or stay within) production use or not, which is not the same thing. For instance, even if a system fails some components of its OQ/PQ testing it still may be acceptable for use if the problems are not critical (i.e. do not affect GCP and regulatory compliance), or a workaround is available, or the system vendor/designer can be persuaded to quickly add or fix the missing functionality. The reality is that the time and money spent on assessing and procuring a system, or building one in-house, and then installing and validating it, are usually far too high for a non-commercial data centre to be able to quickly switch to another system.

The summary documentation should make both the responses to both questions clear: did the system pass or fail the verification of its functionality and if it did not what are the problems and subsequent actions? Is the system suitable for production use, and if so are there any caveats or workarounds that need to be implemented? The evidence for compliance would be the summary statements themselves, against a range of different systems.

Once in use, ongoing system validation activity (e.g. for system updates) and status, should be recorded in the validation inventory.

IT05.06: Change-management policies

Controlled documents should be in place defining risk-based change-management mechanisms.

All systems are subject to change, for instance from user requests or vendor upgrades and patches, and those changes should be managed for systems to retain their validation status.

This standard requires that there are controlled documents that should specify the change management process and procedures, as well as the roles and responsibilities involved, and how it is documented. It also requires that the process is risk-based, i.e. that the change management includes a risk assessment of the possible effects of the change on the system, and thus the possible revalidation that might be required.

The documents are often augmented by sample proformas for requesting changes, carrying out a risk assessment, approving the changes, and documenting how and when they were carried out (see IT05.07). The evidence that this standard has been met would be provided by the controlled documents themselves, together with the associated proformas.

IT05.07: Change and risk evaluation

Changes in IT systems in scope for validation should be documented, and include a documented risk assessment as well as any necessary revalidation results.

If IT05.06 requires that policies are in place that govern change management, this standard simply requires that those policies are used in practice and that there is documentary evidence of this. It also seeks to guarantee that reassessment/revalidation is integrated into the change management process.

Many centres use a 'check-list' approach to change management that allows common issues to be identified and the decisions taken in respect of each to be easily documented. Questions could include:

- How critical is the functionality being changed?
- Who will be affected by the change and in what context?
- What are the possible impacts on other aspects of the centre's functioning?
- Will documentation and/or training need to be revised to reflect the change? The response to the first question in particular will dictate how much revalidation of the relevant parts of the system will be required. Any revalidation would normally generate detailed documentation that would indicate if the relevant parts of the system still functioned as intended, or not, plus a signed and dated summary statement to that effect. Subsequent CAPA-based changes would be documented in a similar way.

Evidence that the standard has been met would include:

- change management documentation that clearly reflected this method of working;
- structures (e.g. test systems in which changes can be rehearsed) that supported it in practice; and
- a discussion with staff to clarify how the systems worked in practice.

IT05.08: Validation of extracted data

Extracted data, however formatted, and the underlying data extraction processes, should be assessed using a risk-based approach to decide upon the level of validation needed to ensure accurate extraction.

The reports and data extraction facilities that many systems come with 'out of the box' will almost always be validated as part of an initial system validation exercise. The problem is that reports and data extractions are often added on an ad hoc basis during the lifetime of a system, and it is easy for these to slip through the validation

net unless there is a deliberate policy to systematically assess the need for possible additional testing.

If, in addition, an extraction process involves locally constructed processing of some kind then that processing will also need validation, and/or the data in the extracted set or report will need to be compared with the original data in the CDMA to check that they match.

This applies most obviously to the extraction process that generates the datasets for analysis. Although the extraction process would be expected to be the same for all trials on the same system, the volume and/or type of data in any specific trial should be considered to see if more detailed testing might be necessary in any particular case, especially for the first trials extracted from the system.

A common practice is to ensure that the extraction process for the analysis datasets generated the correct numbers of subjects, distributed correctly between sites, and that data from the first and last participants in the trial, and possibly in each site, appears to have been correctly extracted.

The approach should be risk-based. Relevant questions might include:

- How are the reports/data extractions used? Are they providing critical clinical data (e.g. SUSAR details), quality management data (e.g. query rates by site) or administrative details (accrual figures)? The possible impact of any error in the output will be a major factor in determining the validation effort required.
- How similar or different are the reports/extractions to others that have been shown to work?
- Are there any special characters or values in the data that might cause existing extraction or reporting mechanisms to work incorrectly even if they are well established?
- How have the reports/data extractions been constructed? Are they standard reports built into the system and used (and, therefore, checked) by a wide variety of users, or are they ad hoc reports only available at a single centre, and perhaps only used by a few individuals at that centre? Do they involve scripts and code generated in-house rather than by the system vendor?
- How complex are the outputs? Are they simple listings or do they contain complex derivations and sub-totals?
- How much transformation of the data was necessary to produce it in the structure and format required? A system that pivots, splits or aggregates data from various sources, or transforms it into another format altogether (e.g. to XML) is more prone to errors than one that simply dumps pre-existing tables into flat files.

- How easy are the outputs to cross-check? Would errors be obvious, e.g. by visual cross-checking with the data in the databases or with data from other sources, or could errors slip through if not checked in detail?

It should be stressed that not every report/extraction needs to be validated, but every distinct report/extraction should at least be assessed to decide if some form of validation should occur.

Many reports can be parameterised, so part of any validation process would be deciding what range of parameters should be checked.

As with all validations, the results should be documented and available for inspection.

The relevant policies, records of risk assessment and the validation documents themselves would then form the evidence that the standard had been met.

IT05.09: Validation of data transformations

Data transformation processes should be validated, using a risk-based approach.

Reports and data extractions often include data transformations when they are generated, but such transformations can also occur in isolation, for instance changing the format of extracted data (e.g. from XML to SAS, or from the internal database structure to SDTM or ADAM) before transferring it to another institution, or in preparing data prior to importing it into the system (e.g. into CSV files ordered in particular ways).

Like reports, data transformations are often added to the centre's processes after initial validation exercises have been carried out on the associated systems. There is, therefore, a similar risk of these being used without any formal evidence that they have been properly validated.

As with other validation tasks, the process should start with a risk assessment, focusing on the process(es) in which a transformation is used, and how critical those processes are to the overall scientific and data management of a study, and considering the same types of factors as listed within IT05.08.

As with reports, when transformations can be parameterised, it is also important to consider what range of parameters should be checked.

As with all validation, results should be documented and available for inspection.

The relevant policies, records of risk assessment and the validation documents themselves would then form the evidence that the standard had been met.

IT06: Local Software Development

The three standards in this section only apply to those centres that develop their own software in-house.

‘Software’ in this context means all types of systems, utilities, code and scripts used to support data management, for instance extraction and reporting routines, complex stored procedures within databases, and trial administration, coding and treatment allocation systems. In some centres the CDMS itself may have been developed locally.

Note that bespoke software usually carries the greatest risk – recognised by the highest classification (5) in the GAMP approach – and thus the greatest validation burden, e.g. when compared to commercial software. The scope of software development may also include statistical programming (see ST02).

In-house systems are subject to the same risk-based validation requirements as any other system, as described in IT05, but they also have specific requirements relating to their development. In particular, it is vital that the centre has the resources to develop and maintain systems properly, and that the systems created are well documented, so that they are not dependent on the staff who created them.

Hence the focus of these three standards is on documentation (IT06.01 and IT06.02) and resourcing (IT06.03). In addition, a number of suggestions for ‘good practice’ in software development are provided.

IT06.01: Documentation of in-house software

Technical documentation should cover system architecture and deployment, configuration details and the characteristics and purposes of individual components (procedures, classes, etc.).

The focus of this requirement is for a top-down overview of any locally produced system and its architecture, including a brief description of each constituent component (different structures will be relevant to different types of software) including inputs and outputs.

The documentation should complement, but not duplicate the more detailed comments that will be found in the code itself (see IT06.02).

Details of deployment, configuration and dependencies (especially if not integral to the build) are especially important, because these are often difficult or impossible to discover from the code itself. They may include details of web server settings, configuration files and their contents, and runtime dependency requirements. Build processes should be scripted or described in sufficient detail for them to be replicated easily.

In total, the level of documentation should be sufficient – when used with the in-line commenting described in IT06.02 – for another competent developer to make sense of the program, start to work on it and deploy it successfully in a reasonably short time (days rather than weeks).

There should be a detailed specification. Traditionally a document, it is increasingly common to support this, and related testing/deployment, within a software development system – see IT05.04.

The evidence would be obtained from examining the relevant documentation. The auditors' judgement is necessarily a subjective one and it is accepted that it is difficult to agree on what is 'sufficient' documentation. There is also an element of risk-assessment required here – standards of documentation may be set higher with more critical systems. It is relatively easy, however, for auditors to identify systems where documentation levels are clearly too low. For that reason, and because of the importance of documentation in supporting any software project, this standard has been included.

IT06.02: Inline commenting

All code, scripts and procedures should include in-line documentation explaining non-obvious aspects of program execution.

The focus of this particular requirement is bottom-up in-line commenting, so that program execution, particularly when it involves non-obvious processing, is adequately described and the function of individual components can be easily identified.

'Inline' here also includes the headers often found above function or class definitions, describing purpose, input and output parameters, and – in the case of functions – when and from where the code is called. There is no expectation that every function or class is so described, or that every action requires explanation, but anything where the function is not obvious from the code and name should be decorated with comments.

Full descriptive names for functions, classes and variables are strongly recommended as a way of drastically reducing the need for additional comments in code.

The level of documentation should be sufficient that – when used with the overview documentation described in IT06.01 – another competent developer could make sense of the program, start to work on it and deploy it successfully in a reasonably short time (days rather than weeks). Different programmers will have different styles of documentation, so some might use in-line commenting for some information which others would put in separate documents (though in the latter

case it would be reasonable to expect in-line references to those documents). The auditors are, therefore, asked to consider the total documentation available when assessing this and the previous standard. The evidence would be obtained from examining the relevant code. The judgement is subjective, but worth attempting because of the importance of this type of documentation. In addition, it is easier, and arguably more important, to identify missing or clearly inadequate commenting, accepting that 'sufficient' is harder to define.

IT06.03: Resources for software development

The unit should have access to sufficient staff and other resources to support in-house development in the long-term.

Within relatively small academic trials units the resources available for IT development can be very limited, sometimes to just one or two people. This can represent a huge risk for the unit – sudden loss of those staff can (at best) freeze development of the systems and (at worst) lead to systems being abandoned altogether.

Good documentation, of both systems and processes, can do a lot to reduce the risks, but too often a small IT team is under such pressure that they do not have the time to produce that documentation.

Note that the centre only needs to 'have access' to IT staff, they do not need to be part of the unit. They could come from a central pool of IT staff, or from a loose co-operative of developers from different departments or even different institutions, all working on the same system. Centres that use and contribute to open-source projects also have access to a greater pool of expertise.

'Other resources' refers to things like training and tools, as well as other physical resources: space, machines, infrastructure support, etc., all of which contribute to the development and maintenance effort. This standard asks the auditors to make a judgement about the resources available to the centre to support its locally developed systems in the longer term, and the risks it might be exposed to by having too much expertise concentrated in too few people.

As with the other standards in this section the judgement is a subjective one, and the resources required will depend on the extent of in-house development. A unit with a single developer may be adequately resourced if all that developer is doing is writing, and fully documenting, reports and extractions on an open-source system with an active user community, all contributing similar components. That single developer would be a completely inadequate resource, however, if they were responsible for an entire CDMS system. In fact, trials units that could not guarantee sufficient developer resources are encouraged to use commercially available CDMS

systems, because in the longer term the total costs of ownership (which are usually dominated by salaries) may be lower.

As with the other standards in this section, IT06.03 has been included more to allow auditors to point out the dangers of clearly inadequate resourcing rather than to trigger long debates about the exact levels of resourcing required. In the context of ECRIN certification, the key requirement is that a centre can maintain continuity of system development and maintenance, even with loss of key staff. It would be difficult to recommend certification of any centre where that was felt not to be the case.

Good practice in software development

Though not required as a standard, there are a variety of development techniques which would help to indicate high-quality practice and which should make systems easier to develop and safer to maintain. Some of these are listed below.

They would not all be applicable to all situations, and opinions can differ about their relative merits. Some might be beyond the resources of a small development team. Nevertheless, the presence of some of these techniques would increase confidence in the quality of in-house development.

- Techniques that promote ‘separation of concerns’ between different parts of a system.
- Use of a source control system that allows branching and release management.
- Programming against interfaces and data repositories rather than fixed components and data sources.
- Use of a unit testing and/or integration tests, and continuous integration of a test regime with a source control system.
- Use of a library of user controls/common modules across systems.
- Regular code reviews and walk-throughs, shared coding.
- Use of a bug tracking system.
- Use of a scripted build and/or deployment scheme.
- Use of scripts for constructing and modifying databases.
- Consistent and effective error/exception handling techniques.
- Consistent and comprehensive logging techniques.

IT07: Management of User Devices

The standards in this section are concerned with devices used by staff to access systems, and include laptop and desktop PCs, tablets, mobile phones, etc. Access to systems using virtual interfaces are excluded, e.g. accessing a secure research environment where only keystrokes are transmitted.

They cover the configuration, management and support of devices, including authentication, protection from external threats such as viruses and malware, loss, and ongoing security patching.

User devices may be provided and managed by the centre, or user ('bring-your-own-device', BYOD). In either case, adequate security must be demonstrated.

Devices may be regarded as 'fixed', such as desktop PCs and printers, or 'mobile', such as laptops, tablets and mobile phones.

IT07.01: Device inventory

Devices used to access and process data must be recorded.

All user devices should be logged on an inventory, including device type, owner (centre, or user if BYOD), manufacturer and model, identifier, current user, and details of final destruction/disposal (see IT07.04). This includes such devices used for remote working.

The evidence for compliance would be the inventory itself.

IT07.02: Supported software

Devices should use supported operating system and application software.

Devices should be running up-to-date versions of operating systems and application software, regardless of whether the centre or user (BYOD) provides the device. Devices should be configured to support automatic security updates unless there is good reason not to.

The centre should be able to monitor user devices and, if necessary, either prevent unsupported devices from being used on the network or to enforce necessary updates.

The evidence for compliance would be a review of reports from monitoring software, if used, or spot checks on specific user devices.

IT07.03: Anti-virus/malware protection

Devices should be protected from anti-virus/malware.

Devices should be running up-to-date versions of anti-virus/malware software, regardless of whether the centre or user (BYOD) provides the device. Devices should be configured to support automatic updates.

The centre should be able to monitor user devices and, if anti-virus/malware software is not up to date, either prevent such devices from being used on the network or to enforce necessary updates.

The evidence for compliance would be a review of reports from monitoring software, if used, or spot checks on specific user devices.

IT07.04: Device encryption

Devices used to store sensitive data should be encrypted.

While it is not usual to recommend storing data on a user device, e.g. rather than on a network share, there may be times when this is unavoidable, or desirable. Disk-encryption should be implemented by default to provide additional protection should data destruction be overlooked when disposing on devices.

The evidence for compliance would be a review of reports from monitoring software, if used, or spot checks on specific user devices.

IT07.05: Device disposal

Devices should be securely disposed of at end of life.

All devices should be securely disposed of when no longer required. This may be via secure wiping of disks, e.g. using degaussing or multi-pass swiping software, or physical disruption, e.g. through grinding to dust. A record of such action should be recorded (it is common for systems and disposal providers to provide certificates) and recorded in the hardware inventory.

The evidence for compliance would be the inventory and destruction certificates.

DM01: Data Management Planning

This section is unusual in that it only consists of a single standard, but it is one that might be considered fundamental to data management. It requires not just that data management plans are used, but that there is also a suitable local template available for constructing such plans. The reason for asking for a template is that it shows the data centre is co-ordinating the use of data management plans and has ensured that they meet its own requirements, rather than leaving it to each individual trial team to create a document with an ad hoc structure.

DM01.01: Use of data management plans and template

Each study should have a data management plan section within its Trial Master File, describing the study-specific elements of data management, structured using a locally created template.

Although different SOPs and other controlled documents will describe the generic procedures for various aspects of data management, there is also a need to describe the study-specific aspects of that management. This is supported by a data management plan (DMP), very often a distinct document, but as a minimum a defined section within the trial master file.

One function of the DMP is to provide a retrospective record of the study-specific aspects of data management, for example the systems used for the databases, the exact locations of files, or the versions of coding systems and data collection instruments used, with this data being added throughout the life of the study. But it also provides an important mechanism for planning, and therefore resourcing, various aspect of data management: the nature of any data transfers, the use of data standards, the methods to be used for data cleaning, the way in which the analysis files will be constructed, the plans for long-term storage, etc. It is, therefore, important to have a locally defined template for the DMP, to structure this planning activity and ensure that all important aspects are covered.

There are two main reasons why data management plans have become more critical in recent years:

- The fact that trials are often more complex and involve data collection from a variety of sources, especially in translational research where specialist laboratories may be used to carry out bio-assays or measure genomic expression. The need to plan how such data should be aggregated with traditional clinical site data has therefore increased.
- The increasing demand from funders and journal editors for researchers to make their datasets available to others, with the data itself becoming an important product of research rather than merely an intermediate step in the

production of a published paper. This demands greater planning for long-term data storage, including possible data preparation steps (e.g. de-identification) and transfer to a dedicated repository.

The template needs to contain sections covering the entire life of the data. The list below gives some commonly used headings:

- Timescales of data collection and analysis. Target accrual figures and expected approximate volumes of data.
- The different sources of the data (clinical sites, the participants themselves, machine generated data, electronic health records, images, etc.) and the nature of the source documentation in each case. Instances where there will be no obvious source documentation need to be highlighted.
- The use of standards for data items (e.g. CDISC CDASH) and data collection instruments (e.g. questionnaires, standardised tests). The versions being used should be clearly indicated.
- Study specific training and guidance materials for data entry and/or management.
- The exact systems, including versions, used for the collection and storage of the data, including their physical location. This may reference other more detailed documents.
- Any variations from the normal roles, responsibilities and processes described by generic SOPs, in the construction of systems and in data management.
- Storage locations of the relevant data and metadata files (within the file system).
- The study-specific rules for any 'self-evident correction' procedures.
- How data quality will be assured – e.g. by using data validation checks on data entry, double data entry or visual monitoring of core items, central statistical monitoring to identify outliers.
- The nature of data transfers to and from the centre and the mechanisms for merging data from different sources.
- The systems to be used for any coding of data, including versions and any study-specific coding rules.
- How the analysis datasets will be constructed/extracted, and the differences in definition, if any, between the analysis data and the data as collected.
- The expected location and duration of storage of data in the long term, and the different responsibilities of the organisations involved.

- Measures to prepare the data for possible secondary reuse, assuming study participants' consent allows this, including planned use of de-identification techniques, organisations involved, etc.

It is stressed that this is only a sample list and that any centre should construct their own DMP template, reflecting its situation and the types of studies that it manages. The existence of a template does not mean that every DMP must contain exactly the same content, but it does mean that every DMP should at least consider the same core set of issues, and expand the relevant sections as required, adding extra sections if necessary.

Evidence that the standard has been met would include the existence of the template and demonstration of its use in at least two studies.

DM02: CDMA – Design, Development and Validation

A CDMA, or Clinical Data Management Application, is a system that supports data entry and management for a specific trial. It includes the databases and files used to store the data and associated notes and queries. It also includes the electronic CRFs (eCRFs) used for data entry and the trial-specific data validation checks, skipping logic and derivations that those eCRFs contain. As depicted in Figure 1, CDMA are built upon an underlying Clinical Data Management System (CDMS), such as OpenClinica, REDCap, Rave, etc., also commonly referred to as Electronic Data Capture (EDC) systems.

Figure 1: The clinical trial technology ‘stack’.

CDMAs are built as trial-specific applications on top of a generic CDMS. The CDMS itself, usually delivered over the internet, uses various applications and services, themselves assembled on the underlying IT infrastructure.

The standards in this section deal with how CDMA and the eCRFs within them are constructed and then validated to ensure that they are ready for use. They, therefore, span the development of a CDMA from conception through to final sign-off of a production-ready system. This cross-disciplinary process is depicted as a flow chart in Figure 2 below, showing both traditional ‘waterfall’ and ‘prototyping’ methods.

The former follows a stepwise process where a formal specification is prepared and approved before moving onto development and testing, and eventual sign-off for production. The latter supports a period of flexible development with ad hoc testing and frequent stakeholder review. Rather than a comprehensive specification document, development makes use of annotated CRFs, extracts of previous similar CDMA, field/edit check libraries, etc., and previous experience.

The objective of both approaches is to create a CDMA that is fit for purpose. The waterfall method can suffer – sometimes badly – from the need to manage numerous changes during the validation phase. These changes may result from

testing, where such tests reveal errors in the original specification (as distinct from errors of implementation, i.e. ‘bugs’), or last-minute changes to the protocol, e.g. due to peer-review feedback – the late stages of clinical trial implementation are often time-pressured.

The prototyping approach can be better suited to these challenges, with changes originating from specification errors or protocol updates being added to the ‘melting pot’ as they arise. Managing such a dynamic environment can be difficult, however, and requires excellent teamworking and communications.

Figure 2: The workflow for CDMA development

If a prototyping methodology is adopted, it is critical that following the flexible development phase, there is a fixed, documented specification from which formal validation can be performed. It is common here to use a (validated) metadata output from the system, though this must be human-readable and equivalent to a typical specification document. Whichever methodology is used, the specification must be formally approved by appropriate parties, typically including statistics (this is the point of definition of the eventual trial dataset), followed by systematic testing, with clear traceability between specification and test evidence.

Once in the formal validation phase, all further changes must be handled using formal change control. The only exception to this might be if the magnitude of the changes required make it preferable to scrap the formal validation and return to prototyping. If such a decision is made then formal validation must start again from scratch – there should be no confusion between the phases.

The complete process needs to be controlled by SOPs and policies, and supported as necessary by forms, spreadsheet templates and – where necessary – more detailed system-specific technical guidance. DM02.01, therefore, requires that such policies exist.

The protocol is the basis for CDMA development and should contain a description of all data and associated flows. The process of ensuring that the CDMA matches the requirements of the protocol, but does not collect unnecessary data, is considered in DM02.02.

The requirement for a formal specification is the subject of DM02.03. Developing such a specification demands input from different professional groups. One of these groups is the system's end users, whose specific input is considered in DM02.04. The process also demands a particular development environment, as described in DM02.05. The specification and construction process should end with a formal approval process, as required by DM02.06.

The validation phase of CDMA development will be based on the specification, as required by DM02.07. It will lead to a set of detailed documentation recording the validation that has taken place and ultimate sign-off to indicate that the system is ready for production use (DM02.08).

It is critical that there is a clear relationship between CDMA and related documentation throughout the system's life cycle. This is discussed in more detail in DM05.03 below.

DM02.01: CDMA development and validation policies

Controlled documents covering the development of CDMA's and CRFs, including their validation, should be in place.

Developing CDMA and the CRFs within them must be done using defined procedures, with tasks and responsibilities clearly delineated and with approval processes clearly described. Supporting quality documents (e.g. forms, templates and checklists) should be available as required.

The policies could be integrated into a single SOP and related documents, or split into different SOPs dealing with different aspects or stages of the process – the details are not important as long as all aspects of the development process are covered. It is usually a good idea to keep system-specific technical details in separate guidance documents, partly because CDMS systems change between versions, partly because a unit may have, or introduce, more than one CDMS. This allows the SOPs to be kept relatively ‘high-level’ and, therefore, less likely to need frequent revision.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be the relevant controlled documents, together with CDMA-specific documents that showed that the policies had been applied in at least two instances.

DM02.02: The CDMA and the protocol

Processes exist to ensure the CDMA specification fully supports the outcome measures and safety requirements in the protocol, but does not ask for unnecessary data.

A fundamental requirement is that the centre works with the sponsor to ensure a clear link between the protocol and the set of CRFs within the CDMA, with the CRFs capturing sufficient data to support the analysis of outcome and safety measures described in the protocol.

Recent EMA guidance [19] makes clear that all trial data and associated flows must be included in the protocol – those not stated may be regarded as GCP-noncompliant. While it may not be necessary – or helpful – to interpret this guidance as mandating inclusion of every single data item, the protocol should include details of all key endpoint and safety data, and summaries of other data, e.g. quality of life tools. Note the scope here is for *all* data, including that collected using CDMS, ePRO, or from laboratory systems, etc.

Making the CDMA specification a cross-disciplinary process is an important way of ensuring this happens, with input from the investigator(s) and statistician(s) particularly important in this respect. One approach is to first use the protocol to specify the data points that the statisticians will need to carry out the required analyses, and then use the annotated protocol, or even a formal set of analysis data requirements, to drive the CRF specification.

In practice, the danger is less often that insufficient data is collected, but rather that too much data is requested, with data points included not because they are necessary to answer the protocol’s questions, but because the data ‘might possibly

be useful one day', or even because they are part of an eCRF reused from an earlier, similar trial.

Collecting too much data runs counter to data minimisation, a principle emphasised in the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) of the EU: "Personal data must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which those data are processed." (GDPR Rec.39; Art. 5(1)(c)) [9]. At least within the EU, collecting unnecessary data is therefore illegal as well as unethical.

Data may of course be deliberately collected for purposes beyond answering the immediate research question – for instance to ensure a disease-specific 'core dataset' is available, that could be integrated with similar datasets from other sources in the future. But when that is the case it should be explicitly mentioned within the protocol and the participant information sheets, so that the consent for trial participation and data processing is fully informed. (If the exact details of post-trial data use are unknown, a separate consent for data sharing should also be obtained [14].)

One way of reducing unnecessary data is to mandate a detailed review of the CDMA's data points by the study statistician, as the chief 'consumer' of that data. Such a review can result in significantly streamlined datasets, leading to reduced CDMA development and validation times.

Whatever the detailed mechanisms used, the centre should be able to describe and demonstrate how the CRFs are developed and/or checked to ensure they match the protocol in this way. The more this aspect of CRF design is made explicit the easier it will be to demonstrate the standard.

Note that ECRIN auditors are not expected to assess the outcomes of this process, i.e. to assess CRFs against their source protocol, partly because in any particular case the sponsor or investigator will usually have the final say about CRF design and partly because of lack of time. The requirement is that the centre should be able to describe and demonstrate the processes of CRF construction and review, and how that is linked to the requirements of the protocols.

DM02.03: Creating a full functional specification

A CDMA design and full functional specification should exist identifying each data item on each CRF (including field names, types, units, data checking logic, conditional skipping, and derivation logic).

The CDMA development is almost always a multi-disciplinary process, following a waterfall or prototyping approach, as outlined in figure 2.

Data management and IT staff may be most concerned with the detailed specification and design on a day-to-day basis, but input from statisticians and

investigators, and others on the trial management team, is also important, as is input from end users (see DM02.05).

Whichever development methodology is adopted, the specification of the system is defined by the protocol. Following the prototyping approach simply offers an easier way to monitor development and check the specification is being interpreted correctly in a series of incremental steps, rather than all at once at the end.

The specification should include details of the data collection schedule, data points, conditional branching ('skipping'), derivation and data validation logic ('edit checks'), as well as additional study-specific aspects like support for coding, e-signatures, source document verification, or email alerts. The specification and the system are then used as the basis of the validation that makes up the second stage of development.

It is critical that the specification, and resulting production system, be fit for purpose, and include all data fields, edit checks, notifications, etc. The specification should be clearly structured and 'human-readable' – this is important if making use of CDMS metadata exports to generate the specification.

The specification should be signed off by members of the cross-disciplinary team – including the trial statistician – unless such approval is gained before deployment to the production system at the end of the validation process (see DM02.06). In many respects, multi-disciplinary sign-off of the specification is preferred, as this is the point where the dataset is defined; noticing that key data items have been missed as a CDMA is just about to be made live is likely to be less convenient.

Sign-off should show name, role and date, and may be digital or wet ink.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- inspection of at least two detailed CDMA functional specifications;
- a discussion with staff to clarify how the specifications are developed; and
- relevant sections of controlled documents.

DM02.04: Isolation of CDMA in development

CDMAs in development should be isolated from, and clearly differentiated from, the CDMA used in production.

A CDMA should be developed within an environment reserved for development and test activity only. The development and production systems should be isolated from each other – there should be no possibility of problems in a developing CDMA spilling over to affect any production system, or users (including IT staff with elevated privileges) inadvertently confusing development and production systems.

This means that a process needs to exist that ‘pushes’ the completed CDMA from the development to test or production environments. This may be through manual export and import of a ‘study definition’ file or files, or an automated publication process initiated through the CDMS. Development, test and production systems should be clearly marked as such on screen (e.g. by the use of distinct colours, labels, etc.).

An additional ‘training’ instance of the CDMA may be used to support user training. This would typically use the same version as the current live CDMA, but should be considered distinct from the testing instance – testing functionality and training users should not be confused.

In an age of virtual or containerised machines, ‘isolated from’ means logically isolated rather than necessarily on different physical hardware. That means distinct URLs for web-based systems, distinct connection strings and other access mechanisms for database servers, and different users and access control systems on the different types of server.

The various combinations of CDMS and CDMA environments are shown in Figure 3 below:

		CDMS environment (supports CDMA)		
		Development	Test	Production
CDMA type	Dev.	Used only for system dev and, unless locally developed, only by the system vendor.	Used for evaluating new system versions, perhaps with copies of existing CDMA.	CDMA dev version e.g. v2.2
	Test			CDMA test version e.g. v2.1
	Training			CDMA training version e.g. v2.0
	Live			CDMA live version e.g. v2.0

Figure 3: Relationship between CDMS and CDMA versions

It is critical to separate the management of the system – which might constitute a CDMS, associated applications and infrastructure – from the CDMA, e.g. evaluation of an updated version of a *system* should not be confused with the testing of a new version of a *CDMA*.

Transparency here gives less room for human error, reduced risk to data integrity, and less suspicion that the validated status of a CDMA might be compromised by some unknown side effect from system testing.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- explanation and demonstration by centre staff of how the CDMA in development were kept logically isolated from production systems; and
- inspection of relevant controlled documents.

DM02.05: Input into CDMA development by end users

Procedures are in place to secure feedback from selected end users on the practicality and ease of use of the CDMA, and to decide when and how such feedback will be sought.

‘End users’ are staff outside the trials unit who, in an eRDC context, will have to use and input data into the system. In general it would not be realistic to expect such users to carry out detailed, systematic testing of the CDMA, but it is reasonable to expect a sample of end users to provide some feedback on the system’s ease of use, for instance how easy it is to understand or navigate, on the practicality of providing the requested data, and on the ease of raising queries, etc.

How much feedback will be necessary, and from whom, will be very much a function of the particular CDMA and the sites in which it will be used. A relatively simple CDMA, deployed only to sites that already have experience of very similar trials, will probably need little or no additional feedback from end users. On the other hand a CDMA that includes novel features or patterns of data collection would benefit from end-user feedback, ideally from different sites with different levels of prior experience. If new sites are being used for a trial, especially if they are from a different country or language group, then user feedback can be very informative in clarifying how the eCRFs will be interpreted and in identifying potential problems. (User feedback could also be integrated with initial user training.)

There is a question about when such feedback should be sought. Feedback can only be obtained at or near the end of the design and CDMA construction process, because there has to be a system to demonstrate – even if using dummy data. The feedback obtained often relates to the system’s design – layout, labels and prompts, colours, ordering of items, etc. Although data item errors may be found and changes may be requested (e.g. in the ranges allowed for lab data), the type of systematic, detailed testing described in DM02.07 is neither appropriate nor realistic, and could not in any case be supervised.

End-user feedback should, therefore, occur near the end of the design and specification phase, after the CDMA system has been constructed, but before the final specification has

been approved and formally validated. It should be suitably structured (e.g. by the use of proformas) rather than simply using informal emails.

If such feedback is sought after approval of the final specification instead, as it sometimes is, and it results in requests for changes, then these will need to be handled by the CDMA change management mechanism, which will be both more complex and less safe than handling such changes within the final phase of the specification phase.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from

- explanation by centre staff of how the level of user feedback is decided for any particular CDMA;
- how the feedback is organised and gathered; plus
- inspection of actual user feedback.

DM02.06: Cross-disciplinary approval of the functional specification

The CDMA's design and functional specifications are signed off and dated by signatories representing a cross-disciplinary team.

Once the CDMA's final specification is assembled it will need to be formally approved and signed off by the key individuals involved with the trial. The initial version of the CDMA may have been constructed at this stage, if following a prototyping approach, which can facilitate obtained early end-user feedback (see DM02.05), as well as automatic generation of the specification document (though note caution described in DM02.03 regarding format, etc.).

Because developing CDMA's and the CRFs within them should involve the various users of the system, or key representatives of those users, the final sign-off should represent a cross-disciplinary team. As a minimum, the expectation is that a representative of those collecting the data (i.e. the trial's data management staff), those analysing the data (i.e. the trial statistician), and those sponsoring the trial, (a sponsor representative and/or chief investigator) sign off the functional specification. Others who are usefully included in the sign-off are those building the CDMA (i.e. the IT staff), and a quality assurance or operational manager.

The cross-disciplinary approval does not necessarily mean that all parties will check the specification for the same things. In most cases, for instance, it would be unreasonable to expect the chief investigator to look through every data item in detail, but they should at least be satisfied that the main outcome and safety measures are properly covered. As described in DM02.02, statisticians may be asked to check that no unnecessary data is being collected, as well as confirming that the obtained data will be fit for their analysis. A data manager will probably check the

eCRFs in detail, and confirm that feedback has been confirmed from end users, while the unit's quality manager may also check for adherence to unit policies on CDMA design, use of coding systems, etc. Some of this assessment can be done by inspecting the system itself, but some of it will require checking of more detailed documents.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- inspection of the relevant controlled document;
- a discussion with staff to clarify how the CDMA's were developed; and
- the range of names and signatures involved in signing off CRF specifications.

DM02.07: CDMA validation against the functional specification

Systematic, detailed testing is carried out against the functional specification for each CDMA before deployment to the production environment.

The newly constructed version 1.0 of the system needs to be validated against the approved functional specification, to check that it really does match that specification and is, therefore, fit for purpose.

As well as checking the more obvious features like data type, captions, tab order and code lists for each data item, this means going systematically through the system to check the skipping logic, derivation logic, and each of the data validation checks.

Problems found at this stage are, by definition, bugs rather than design faults, because the design has been fixed. As noted in DM02, however, it might be that design errors are discovered during formal testing. Such issues should be managed through change control, i.e. a change request raised, update implemented and tested, and approved as an updated version. To avoid confusion, it might be sensible to bundle any such change requests together and deal with these in a clean new version, after the current testing is complete. If change requests become significant then this may be a sign that approval to proceed to formal testing came too soon; it may be simpler to scrap the current formal testing and 'return to the drawing board' – reducing the likelihood of this eventuality is seen as one of the benefits of a flexible development process.

Systematic testing can be a lengthy and rather mechanical exercise, and may, therefore, be carried out by relatively junior staff. That is acceptable as long as the specification and any additional instructions are clear and there is sufficient supervision. Validation should not be carried out by anyone who constructed the CDMA because misinterpretations of the original requirements may simply be repeated.

Using data managers for CDMA validation has the advantage of raising awareness of the system before use. This may not be the best use of skilled staff time, however, and should not be confused with the GCP requirement for effective training.

Some CDMA's may require additional testing for particular functionality (like coding, or message triggering) that is specific to the study definition. The testing should also be included in the validation because these features should be described within the specification.

Critical thinking should be applied to CDMA validation – testing every item of functionality in the same way may neither be necessary or effective, e.g. where unaltered fields and/or edit checks are imported from a previously-validated CDMA, say for a fixed quality-of-life questionnaire. Solid evidence is needed here to ensure confidence can be assured.

Greater efforts should be directed at key endpoint data, or data impacting patient safety. A risk-assessment methodology should be documented and applied, e.g. assigning fields as high, standard or low risk. The default strategy should be described in the SOP dealing with the validation process, but study-specific decisions about validation need to be described and justified (in the DMP) to the extent that they vary from this default position.

In addition to systematic testing it is worth considering the use of ad hoc testing, especially by expert users. Such users, given a remit to 'try to break the system', will often find issues that elude those following a prescribed script. Recently updated GAMP guidance [20] provides useful practical detail and support for the use of such testing.

Evidence of all testing, together with findings, should be documented. This should include the specific test case – either prospectively described, or noted during ad hoc testing – whether the test passed or failed, the nature of the failure, together with details of the user and the date of testing.

It is not acceptable to describe a test by simply listing the field name, or using vague terms like 'check field behaves as expected' – the test condition should provide a clear description of the test performed and the expected outcome, e.g. 'enter date in future, warning message should be shown as per specification'. Such transparency should make clear the meaning of the pass/fail outcome.

It is not necessary to capture screenshots unless this is helpful to the testing process, i.e. makes clear the nature of the problem, particularly to the developer who may be asked to fix it. Neither is it necessary to record the date and user against each specific test, if it is obvious that the same user executed all tests recorded on the document on the same day.

It is likely that multiple cycles of testing will be needed. Such cycles should be clearly segregated and recorded, most usefully on separate documents, e.g. cycle 1, cycle 2, cycle 3, with the expectation that the number of tests executed should decline markedly through the cycles, and such cycles should show logical chronology, i.e. cycle 1 precedes cycle 2. Attempting to document multiple rounds of testing on a single document is not advised as it can quickly become complicated, with chronology difficult to interpret, especially by an auditor.

At the end of the exercise all issues should be resolved, so that it can be shown that the system meets its functional specification. If the process generates requests for design changes, i.e. the specification itself needs to change, the change management process needs to be used to assess the risk associated with the change (usually low at this stage because there is no real data in the system) and thus the additional validation required (see DM02).

All the detailed test documentation/systems, as well as the results, and any scripts, dummy data, listings, etc., used for any particular validation should be retained. Much of this may be in electronic form rather than on paper.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- examples of completed test documentation (for at least two trials, dated and with the staff involved identified); and
- a discussion with staff to clarify how the validation process was organised in practice.

DM02.08: CDMA final sign-off into production

Each CDMA should be formally approved, dated and signed off by the relevant signatories before production use.

Once CDMA validation has been successfully completed there should be documented approval for release into the production environment.

As noted in DM01.02, ideally the specification sign-off should be by the cross-disciplinary team, and if this approach has been adopted, sign-off to make the new CDMA live might be sought from a senior member of the trial team, effectively just noting that due process has been followed, i.e. the validation has been performed according to expected quality standards.

If the specification has not been signed off by the cross-disciplinary team, particularly the trial statistician, then this must be completed before the CMDA goes live.

Sign off should show name, role and date, and may be digital or wet ink.

It may be helpful to include a validation summary report, if say the system is to be made live with some unresolved issues.

Evidence that the standard has been met will be appropriately signed and dated documents confirming that a CDMA meets its specification and can be used as a production system.

Standards and reuse of items and forms as indicators of good practice in CDMA design and development

Listed below are several examples of ‘best practice’ in CDMA development and CRF. They do not form part of the ECRIN requirements, but their use provides greater confidence that procedures for CRF creation are well developed and applied consistently.

- Use of form or field libraries (e.g. quality of life questionnaires, blood results) may improve data quality and reduce validation efforts, if it can be clearly shown that an imported CRF is identical to the library version, and that it has already been thoroughly tested (evidence should be available). Any CDMA-specific customisation, e.g. cross-CRF edit checks, should of course be dealt with separately. Libraries should be carefully curated – strict version control is essential to maintain clarity and quality – and use supported by guidance documents.
- Use of standard coding systems, either domain-specific (e.g. CDASH [15]) or local, can improve data quality and make systems easier to use, e.g. consistent use of 1=Yes, 2=No, coding of missing data, preference for positive formulated questions.
- Local guidance documents specifying good design practice and preferred orientation, colours, fonts, graphics, positioning, etc., (as far as the CDMS allows variation in these) can promote consistency and a ‘house style’. Consistent and sensible use of dividers and sectioning, and white space, can also add to consistency and the ease of use of systems.

DM03: CDMA – Change management

Once the specification for a CDMA has been approved, and thus fixed, any further changes to that specification will need to be considered within a formal change management process. If the process described in DM02 is followed, such changes should only occur once the system has been validated against its specification, and signed into production, and the change management process is designed to ensure that the system retains its validation status.

The change management required follows the general principles outlined in IT05 (standards IT05.06 and IT05.07 in particular), but CDMA change is relatively common, and its proper management critical to data management, so a separate section of standards is justified.

DM03.01: Change management of CDMA

Controlled documents for CDMA change management are in place.

- Controlled documents should be in place dealing with CDMA change management, detailing procedures, roles and responsibilities and documentation.
- Suggestions for clear, chronological nomenclature for documentation and CDMA versions, are described in DM03.05.
- Evidence that the standard has been met will be the controlled documents themselves.

DM03.02: Documenting change requests

Individual requests for change to CDMA are justified, itemised and documented.

The initial step in the change management process is to ensure that any requests for change to the CDMA are accurately described and authorised. This might involve a paper or screen-based proforma being completed, or request logged within a software management system, with the necessary specification for and justification for the request.

It should be clear which version of the CDMA specification the change applies to (see DM03.05).

Evidence that the statement has been met would be from inspection of proformas or software management system (or output). Note the importance of ensuring human-readable formatting if using the latter – it is not acceptable to offer a complicated, unformatted, or otherwise unintelligible text output!

DM03.03: Change and risk analysis

A risk analysis is conducted and recorded when considering any change.

The change management process must include an assessment of the potential impacts and risks associated with a proposed change. For relatively trivial changes (font size or help text say) these impacts may be small; for substantial changes, e.g. the addition of a new eCRF, they may be considerable.

Changes that would risk orphaning data already in the system (e.g. dropping questions or categories) or making existing data invalid (e.g. changing the type of a question) should not normally be allowed and the change request should be rejected.

Any change will impact the CDMA itself, but there may also be impacts 'downstream', for instance on the data extraction process or the scripts used during statistical analysis, or on system documentation and/or user training. A CDMA change may also imply a change to the protocol (see DM03.07).

It is important that all these aspects are considered. Some centres use a 'change checklist' approach to structure the assessment of risk and to help with its documentation.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be the inspection of the risk assessment documentation against a range of proposed CDMA changes.

DM03.04: Testing of CDMA changes

Any change is tested in the development/test environment and the test results are recorded.

The risk analysis (see DM03.03) will determine the amount and type of revalidation required. This should always take place on the test CDMA version (probably one version ahead of the live CDMA) in the production environment. The standard approach (i.e. as used in the initial formal testing) should be followed, with tests, outcome and acceptance clearly documented).

It may be tempting to make and inspect trivial changes directly in the live CDMA – this should be avoided as the flow of versions between the two environments is disturbed, and clear separation lost between test and live CDMA's.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from inspection of the detailed test results relating to changes.

DM03.05: Versioning

Clear and consistent versioning should be used for the CDMA and related documentation.

As part of the development, deployment and change management processes, different versions of CRFs and associated documents will exist and need to be carefully and clearly managed. It should be obvious how versions of component documentation relate to one another, and to the CDMA itself, and whether the version relates to approved or draft documents, specification updates or bug fixes.

Systematic use of file nomenclature may facilitate chronology and interpretation – a suggested approach is described in more detail at the end of this section.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from inspection of the CRFs and relevant specification documents, CDMA, and a discussion of version management in the centre.

DM03.06: Communicating changes

Mechanisms are in place to inform relevant staff and users of changes, and provide support and explanatory material as required.

The potential impact of any change on users should also be considered. In most cases data entry staff will need to be informed of changes and why they have been introduced, and so mechanisms should be in place to allow this to happen consistently.

For substantial changes there may also be a need to provide additional training, and the communication should reflect that.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from explanation by centre staff of how the system worked, from the relevant parts of controlled documents and from examples of the mechanism in action.

DM03.07: Changes and protocol revision

Mechanisms should exist to ensure any requested CDMA change that implies a protocol amendment is identified.

An amendment to the study protocol can often generate changes in the study's CDMA. That is normally a straightforward process, because it is the direction in which change would be expected to flow.

From time to time, however, a requested CDMA change may represent or imply a change to the protocol, even though it may not have been presented or recognised as such. For example, the centre might be notified of a change to a normal lab

range. The centre should have a mechanism in place to ensure that any change that implied a protocol amendment (that had not already been proposed) would be identified. The amendment would then need to be managed before the CDMA itself was changed. For instance, any necessary reapprovals would need to be obtained before the CDMA change was implemented in the production system.

It is recognised that for many centres this type of change request would be rare, but there is no harm in including a checking mechanism within the process of reviewing and approving requested changes, and recording the decision made (for instance as part of a 'change checklist').

[It might also be useful to record, as part of the change management process, the more normal situation where a requested CDMA follows a protocol amendment, and if so which one.]

Evidence that this standard has been met would come largely from inspection of the relevant controlled documents and associated proformas, together with a discussion of any examples of the mechanism being used in practice.

Suggestions for clear document nomenclature

A systematic file naming convention may facilitate chronology and interpretation, i.e. such that filenames may be easily ordered to follow the development pathway, and that the purpose of each document is clear. Such an approach is provided below; it is not mandatory to adopt this, or any other systematic format, but it may help to do so.

The different components of the file name are separated by underscore ('_'); decimals are used to indicate drafts, whole numbers for live documents. Decimal points are replaced with a dash ('-') to avoid confusion with file extensions (e.g. '.docx').

- BigTrial_Spec_v0-1 – first draft spec (v0.1) for the Big Trial
- BigTrial_Spec_v0-2 – second draft spec (v0.2)
- BigTrial_Spec_v1 – first spec version (v1), ready for testing
- BigTrial_Spec_v1_TestLog1 – first round of testing
- BigTrial_Spec_v1_TestLog2 – second round
- BigTrial_Spec_v1_TestLog3 – third and final round
- BigTrial_Spec_v1_xSignOff – v1 sign-off to go live (note 'x' simply ensures file follows chronology in alphabetised list)
[System now live, labelled v1, as per associated spec]
- BigTrial_Spec_v1_zBugFix1_TestLog1 – v1 bug 1 testing (note no change in spec version here, this is a bug; z used to enforce chronology)

- BigTrial_Spec_v1_zBugFix1_xSignOff – sign-off for bug fix
- BigTrial_Spec_v1-1 – first draft amendment to live system
- BigTrial_Spec_v2 – approved amendment, signed-off
- BigTrial_Spec_v2_TestLog1 – first round of testing for spec v2
- BigTrial_Spec_v2_TestLog2 – second and final round
- BigTrial_Spec_v2_xSignOff – sign-off to go live
- BigTrial_Spec_v2_zBugFix1_TestLog1 – testing v2 bug fix
- BigTrial_Spec_v2_zBugFix1_xSignOff – sign-off for v2 bug fix
- BigTrial_Spec_v2-1 – v2.1, draft spec amendment

In this way, the chronology of development and release is maintained and obvious to a user – or auditor – something that should reduce opportunity for confusion, or stress when being inspected.

Folders might be used to segregate documentation relating to different versions (note that the draft spec amendment to v1 resides in the v2 folder, as it should do). Associated documentation chronology should then be clear – see Figure 4 below.

The CDMA should also display, perhaps as a header or on the home page, the corresponding version of the specification, and any subsequent updates associated with bug fixes (i.e. without spec version change), for example:

- v1.0 – first live version of CDMA (corresponds to v1 spec)
- v1.0.1 – first bug fix to v1 (no change to spec)
- v1.0.2 – second bug fix to v1
- v2.0 – second version of CDMA (corresponds to v2 spec)
- v2.0.1 – first bug fix to v2.0

This approach should make clear the ongoing relationship and chronology between documentation and CDMA throughout its life cycle, something likely to facilitate communication, reduce risk of error, and ease inspection burden.

Figure 4: Suggested file nomenclature showing clear chronology

DM04: Site Management, Training and Support

These standards apply to the preparation and support of site staff by the staff of the data centre with regard to data management and IT systems, and data entry and query management in particular. They are not directly concerned with overall site management issues such as site regulatory or ethical approval (though this is an indirect issue in DM04.04).

DM04.01: Policies for site opening and support

Controlled documents for opening and supporting a site for data collection are in place.

Preparing and supporting site staff is a key function of any data centre and must be covered by relevant controlled documents. These would need to deal with (for instance) the training and preparation of site staff, the triggers that allow access to production systems, the provision of documentation and ongoing support for sites.

The evidence would be the controlled documents themselves.

DM04.02: User training for data entry

User training with data entry instructions or guidelines, for pCRFs and/or eCRFs, is provided for site staff.

Site research staff will need adequate preparation to correctly use pCRFs and/or eCRFs, delivered by preparatory training sessions, and/or self-study training material, written guidance, onscreen prompts and help documentation. The amount of preparation will vary with the level of experience of site staff and the complexity and/or novelty of the study.

The evidence that this standard is met will come from the records of training sessions and the distribution of training materials, and a discussion with staff to clarify how the training is applied in practice.

DM04.03: Isolation of training eCRFs

Access to the CDMA for training purposes is managed to ensure that it is isolated from access to clinical data.

Users need to have the opportunity to train on CDMA, generally using dummy or test data, but it is important that this data is kept separate from actual study data.

User access for training purposes must, therefore, be managed to ensure that this is the case, ideally through a dedicated training instance of the latest CDMA version (see DM02.04). If such a system is used, the difference between live and training

environments should be obvious to users, through background colour, banner header, etc.

Use of a dummy ‘training site’ within the live CDMA is discouraged as data from the site must then be excluded from the analysis dataset (during or after the extraction process). If such an approach must be adopted then obviously false site names and codes, and participant identifiers, should be used. Some systems allow for site-dependent visibility of on-screen features or labels, again allowing the distinction to be clearer.

Though included here in the standards for site staff, the same consideration also applies to internal centre staff who input data for paper-based trials, and who need initial familiarisation with the trial’s CDMA.

The evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- explanation and demonstration by centre staff of how the data generated in training was kept separate from actual study data;
- inspection of relevant controlled documents; and
- demonstration of the differences between production and training eCRFs.

DM04.04: Site access to production system

A site is given access to a production CDMA only after the sponsor, or the sponsor’s representative, has confirmed that all relevant preparation, permissions and agreements have been completed.

For eRDC trials the production CDMA should not be available to a site until that site has been fully prepared and approved. That normally means that all contractual agreements have been signed, normally by both the site and the sponsor (or the data centre acting on the sponsor’s behalf) and the relevant organisational and ethical approvals are in place.

Individuals, assuming they are properly prepared themselves (see DM04.05), should only be given access to the production system after the overall site preparedness has been confirmed. Unique user accounts should be created such that user activity, e.g. adding and updating data, may be linked to an individual; shared accounts are not acceptable.

It is the sponsor’s responsibility to make the decision about a site’s preparedness. The data centre may be part of the same organisation, or be acting for sponsor in this respect, but in general the sponsor needs to inform the centre when a site is ‘ready to go’, and policies and procedures should reflect this.

For paper-based trials the ‘production CDMA’ at the site is effectively the set of pCRFs, which may be delivered during the preparatory phase. pCRFs should not be accepted from the site, however, until it has been officially opened.

The evidence that the standard has been met would come from the relevant controlled documents, and demonstration by centre staff of how and when actual sites have been opened.

DM04.05: Individual access to production system

Individuals have access to production data only when they have been trained with the CDMS and the specific CDMA.

The centre should be confident that site staff can use the system properly and accurately in the context of any particular CDMA. There is no requirement for a formal exam or test. The input could be:

- Training provided at the site by data centre staff or monitors.
- Demonstrations across the web, or pre-recorded videos.
- Training material and manuals. Many centres create a generic training manual for their system(s), and then add study-specific data entry instructions to that for each study.
- Provided at the site by more experienced or specialist site staff (‘super users’) who can then provide guidance and training for new or less experienced staff.

In practice, two or three of these methods are often used together.

To allow the competence of staff to be assessed, and to allow the staff to develop confidence themselves, most centres provide a training version, or – more normally – a dummy ‘training site’ for each study. Initially, users are given access only to the training site, where they can add dummy patients and try out different data values, see how the system operates, how alerts and messages work, etc. Of course, when the data is extracted for analysis any subjects and data in the dummy site are removed.

This scheme allows the users to demonstrate they have entered data for a few patients in the dummy system, and that they are happy with using the system before they are given access to their normal site data. If necessary, the centre can check the accuracy of their input. If the user comes across things that they do not understand in the dummy site, they are able to input different values to see the effects of that, and/or contact the data centre for guidance.

It is difficult to describe a system that will fit every situation. Many centres specialise in trials of a certain type or disease area, and often use the same clinical

sites repeatedly. In these cases only a small amount of training might be required, just to cover any trial-specific aspects. On the other hand, if a centre has set up a very complex trial and is using some sites for the first time, users will probably need more training and checking before they are allowed on the production system.

The evidence for the standard being met would include the centre demonstrating it had systems in place for controlling access and for determining the most appropriate training and checking methods for any specific study, and the demonstration of some of those methods in practice.

DM04.06: Site documentation

Processes exist to update and redistribute site documentation when this is required as part of change management.

A site will need to store documentation relevant to the trial – particularly the protocol and guidance material related to completing the pCRFs/eCRFs. Should the protocol and/or CDMA change, those documents will need revision and redistribution to sites and mechanisms need to be in place to support this. Formal approval must precede any change to documentation.

Evidence would come from demonstration of the mechanisms in action, usually within the CDMA change management process (see DM03.06).

DM04.07: Responsibility list

Processes exist to assure that up-to-date information about who can do what at each site, including entering data and/or signing off CRFs, is available to data centre staff.

Centres need to know not only which staff at each site should have access to the production system, but also what the responsibilities of those staff are within the trial, allowing them to check that only properly authorised staff carry out tasks, for instance completing CRFs, carrying out the treatment allocation procedure, or completing a SAE form. If staff leave or are away for a reason (particularly the site's principal investigator) the centre needs to know to whom their duties have been delegated.

In short, the centre needs to keep copies of what are often known as 'delegate logs', covering the staff for each site in the trial. The principal investigator at the site has the responsibility for creating and maintaining the log and ensuring that staff are suitably qualified for their role, but the centre should have a copy of the resultant list of named site staff and their roles within the study. How the logs are obtained and then kept up to date will differ from centre to centre – some may use monitoring or other visiting staff to keep them informed of changes, others may ask site staff to

send the details in directly to trial managers. Either way the requirement is that a list is available to data entry and trial management staff.

Evidence that the standard has been met will be:

- the presence of lists of staff and responsibilities for sites; and
- controlled documents that describe how such lists are obtained and kept up to date as much as possible.

DM04.08: User support – prompt response

The centre is able to provide Help Desk support and/or web-based support (details as agreed with sponsors) to provide a rapid initial response to site requests.

User support needs to be maintained during the course of the trial, and that includes a prompt response to queries or requests for help from site staff. Such support might involve a telephone hotline or it may be a web-based system.

The precise nature of this support will depend on the judgement of the centre and the trial sponsor, and the resources that have been made available to provide it. The requirement is that the centre is able to provide some form of prompt user support when resourced to do so.

As evidence that this is the case, centre staff would normally be expected to provide examples of current support agreements and mechanisms.

DM04.09: User support – in English

Help desk/web support can be provided in English as well as the data centre’s native language.

In multinational trials user queries and requests may arrive in a variety of languages. No centre can be expected to support all the potential languages staff might use in a cross-European trial, but there is a requirement that they can provide such support in English at least.

Evidence would come from direct observation.

DM05: Data Entry and Processing

The standards in this section deal with data entry into the CDMA. Most modern CDMS make this very straightforward, but, as one of the core processes of data management, it still requires a framework of policies and procedures if it is to be carried out consistently to agreed standards.

DM05.01: Data entry policies

Controlled documents for data entry and corrections are in place.

Some of these documents may be generic (e.g. general policies on using self-evident corrections) but others may be trial-specific and usually found within the Data Management Plan for the trial (e.g. the specific self-evident corrections that have been prospectively agreed as acceptable).

Evidence that the standard has been met would be the controlled documents themselves.

DM05.02: Production of interim CRFs

For trials/sites using eCRFs, procedures should be in place to generate accurate iCRFs (interim CRFs) for sites, if and when necessary.

A centre should be able to generate so called interim CRFs or iCRFs if required and if the sponsor agrees this would be appropriate. These are paper representations of the data capture screens.

They may be needed in eRDC systems if immediate data entry into the system is not possible or desirable during initial data collection. Anecdotal evidence suggests that this is a common situation, especially as many site staff find it difficult, and rather unsympathetic, to interview subjects and use an eRDC system at the same time. iCRFs may also be helpful where network connectivity is poor or absent, such that direct data entry is not practicable.

In such circumstances research staff at the site are far safer using structured paper documents that match the eCRF to note down responses and other data, rather than blank sheets of paper or whatever else might be available. The system should, therefore, be able to produce such iCRFs, ideally directly at the site ('system' being all available systems and processes, including but not limited to the CDMS).

In some cases the iCRFs can be as simple as screenshots of the eCRF screens, though they should include a mechanism for noting the subject's name, number or similar unique identifier. The important thing is that they allow data collection to be structured in the same way as if the eCRF was directly available, and safely stored before it is transferred to the eRDC system.

It should be noted that use of iCRFs may compromise data quality by creating two tiers of data collection, direct and via the iCRF, the latter effectively becoming a pCRF, and potentially a source document. Use of iCRFs should be described in the protocol.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- explanation and demonstration by centre staff of how interim CRFs could be created; and
- inspection of relevant controlled documents, detailing the procedures to be followed.

DM05.03: Management of missing data (eRDC)

Mechanisms are in place to identify and report on missing or late eCRF data.

(This standard only applies to centres running eRDC trials.)

Monitoring what data has arrived is part of the data entry process, so that sites can be contacted to request missing or late data. Some eRDC systems make this straightforward, with the system set up to identify missing data and the centre able to send messages to sites to query that data. Others focus on data collection rather than the workflow, so data may need to be exported and processed, perhaps using statistical scripts, before missing or late data can be identified.

The exact mechanism is, therefore, likely to depend on the sophistication of the eRDC system(s). A useful feature of scheduling systems within eRDC system is the ability to suppress missing data messages when notification is received that the subject has died or is lost to follow-up. This avoids irritating sites by requesting data that will never exist.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- the relevant controlled documents; and
- demonstration of the missing/late data management system(s) and explanation of their use in practice.

DM05.04: Management of missing data (paper CRFs)

Mechanisms are in place to identify and report on missing or late paper CRFs.

(This standard only applies to centres running paper-based trials.)

With trials using paper CRFs there is often a lag (from several days to several weeks) between CRF receipt and the addition of the data to the CDMS, so that the CDMS cannot be used reliably to monitor receipt of data. It is, therefore, necessary to have

a separate CRF tracking system in place, unless the lag time can be guaranteed to be limited to a few days.

A useful feature of CRF tracking systems is the ability to automatically truncate a subject's schedule when notification is received that the subject has died or is lost to follow-up, or at least allow easy manual amendment. This avoids irritating sites by requesting data that will never exist. This is not currently part of the standard, but is regarded as best practice.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- the relevant controlled documents; and
- demonstration of the pCRF tracking system and its outputs.

DM05.05: Handling patient identifying information

Inappropriate patient identifying information submitted to the centre is obscured or removed.

One of the problems that can occur in data entry is patient identifying information being inappropriately added to, or retained on, submitted data. For instance, with paper CRFs, site personnel may add the patient's name or initials to a safety report, or annotate a CRF or image file with local identifiers; radiological images may include patient names. With eRDC, names are sometimes entered in error into comments, notes, and query responses, etc.

In some cases this may contravene national regulations, in others the policy of the centre and/or sponsor. In either case the identifiers should be removed, either by requesting that site staff delete the data (EDC) or obfuscate it (pCRFs, e.g. using black marker pen). Site staff should be reminded of the requirement to omit such identifiers. Note that with the former, the original data will be retained in the EDC audit trail, though this data is typically only visible to the site staff who entered it, and limited CTU staff.

In either case the centre should be able to demonstrate general and/or study-specific policies describing the appropriate actions to take, and their application in use. The evidence that the standard has been met would come from:

- relevant controlled documents; and
- a discussion with staff and demonstration of the blinding being put into action.

DM05.06: Audit trail

All transactions in the CDMS (insert, update, delete) must have an audit trail, covering the date and time of the input, the person making the change, the old and new values, and reason for the change.

Providing an audit trail of the CDMS transactions is a regulatory requirement. For instance, the FDA requires the “Use of secure, computer-generated, time-stamped audit trails to independently record the date and time of operator entries and actions that create, modify, or delete electronic records. Record changes shall not obscure previously recorded information.” [16]. Modern CDMSs invariably support such an audit trail.

GCP regards the recording of ‘reason for change’ as optional (section 4.9.3 notes that changes should be explained ‘if necessary’), a view reaffirmed in the recent guidance from EMA [19] (reason should be recorded ‘if applicable’). A risk-proportionate decision should be taken on a trial-specific basis, with discrete reasons agreed and documented in the data management plan.

Most data centres will already be making use of CDMS audit trails as part of routine monitoring (see 05.08 and 06.11 below).

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from demonstration of the audit trail being created in a test database.

DM05.07: Timestamp control

Sites using eRDC should not be able to change the CDMS’s timestamp.

Because an accurate timestamp is an integral part of the audit trail, it is important that there is no ambiguity about the time recorded against data activity. In particular it should only be possible to set this time centrally, i.e. at the data centre, and not at the remote sites.

Most CDMSs support this feature automatically, and also record both the local time at the data centre and the time at the remote site inputting data, usually as the data centre time +/- n hours according to the site’s time zone.

Evidence that the standard has been met would normally come from the CDMS documentation and demonstration of the use of local/site times within the data.

DM05.08: Audit trail review

Procedures for risk-based, trial-specific audit trail reviews should be in place and outcomes documented.

Audit trail review is now seen as another component in the data management toolbox and offers additional opportunities for data monitoring over and above traditional in-built management of missing data and custom edit checks (e.g. out of range values) found in CDMS.

Audit trail review might be used to detect signs of unwanted manipulation, data entered/updated at unexpected hours and dates, unauthorised access or inconsistent processing of data. It can also be used to detect device or system malfunction. The audit trail here might be expanded to include metadata such as access or system logs, events, etc.

The nature of the trial-specific audit trail review should be documented in the data management plan and updated as necessary throughout the trial. Efforts should be focused on key endpoint and safety data, and aligned with central statistical monitoring activity (see 06.11).

Investigators should be made aware of how to access and navigate audit trail data in order to review their own data.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from review of the data management plan and audit trail review outcome documents.

DM06: Managing Data Quality

A data centre should be able to run checks on the accuracy and consistency of the data it contains, during and after data entry. There should also be mechanisms, involving raising queries with the clinical sites, to resolve any discrepancies, or potential discrepancies.

The standards in this section cover this area, but they are concerned only with the data quality activity that takes place at the data centre – they exclude those that take place at sites, and specifically they exclude monitoring and source document verification (SDV) even though these are important mechanisms for checking data quality. They do include, however, the support that the centre might provide for SDV and monitoring.

Data checking may take place during data entry into a CDMS: using preconfigured consistency and range checks after data entry, but still using tools within the CDMS; after data entry, but using manual checking of source paper records and database values or double data entry; or after data export and subsequent analysis, usually by scripts written in statistical software. The standards cover all these types of checking mechanisms though, of course, only some of them would be used by any particular centre.

Query management is usually integrated into modern CDMSs, with queries raised, annotated, responses reviewed and the queries closed all on screen, the CDMS acting as the transport medium between centre and sites. For paper-based trials queries must be raised and tracked separately in some centres using IT systems developed for the purpose, in others more basic tools like spreadsheets. The standards in this section apply to both types of query management.

DM06.01: Data quality policies

Controlled documents are in place describing the various ways in which the centre maximises data quality.

These documents will cover (for instance) data checking mechanisms, both within CDMA and outside them, query generation, tracking and resolution, and the support of site monitoring (but not the monitoring process itself). For centres managing paper-based trials there should also be policies about quality control of the transcription process from paper CRF to the CDMS.

Data queries are typically sent to site staff for investigation and response, but may also be directed at other data providers, e.g. laboratories.

It is recognised that in any particular case the details of the data checking regime might be modified by the sponsor and/or trial management team (and be described

in the study-specific data management plan) but there should be default policies and procedures in place.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be the controlled documents themselves.

DM06.02: Data checks during data entry

It should be possible to include data checking mechanisms within the data entry process.

As a minimum it should be possible to apply range checks on numeric and date data items. These may be either ‘soft’, i.e. they generate a warning (e.g. lab value out of normal range), or ‘hard’, i.e. they reject the data value entirely (e.g. ‘date of birth cannot be in the future’), or some combination of both. The use of ‘hard’ checks in paper-based studies is unwise, because it may stop a received value being input into a database, but they can be useful within eRDC systems.

Data entry checks would also normally include other conditions that could be easily set up on a single data item, such as set membership (e.g. ‘value is one of 1,2,3,4 or 5’) or matching a regular expression (‘this does not appear to be a valid email’).

Of course, many CDMS systems allow much more complex checks than these to be set up. Many allow data items on different forms and visits to be compared for consistency and also allow complex expressions to be evaluated. There is, however, a debate about the time and effort it takes to set up and test complex checks in many CDMS, compared (for instance) to doing them within scripts in a statistical package.

The level and complexity of checks used will vary from study to study, and will also tend to vary inversely with the number and complexity of checks carried out post-data entry. Data centres exhibit wide variations in the emphasis they put on checking data during and after data entry, but they should have mechanisms available to do both, and be able to demonstrate both in action. The evidence that the standard has been met would be:

- demonstration of simple checks on a variety of eCRFs; and
- a discussion with centre staff explaining their use of data entry checks.

DM06.03: Data checks post-data entry

Pre-programmed data checking procedures are available to be used post-data entry.

This can involve a variety of mechanisms. The most flexible method is to periodically export the data so that scripts can be run against it, usually using a statistical package such as SAS, R or Stata, to identify outliers, inconsistent values, missing values, etc.

Many CDMS also allow pre-planned validation checks to be run against datasets, often referred to as ‘batch validation’. This may happen periodically, but it is particularly useful if a new data entry check is added to a system and needs applying to the data that has already been entered.

The more traditional method is to export selected data points into a simplified format, often in a spreadsheet, to form ‘line listings’. These can then be visually inspected for inconsistent or extreme values.

Unfortunately, used in isolation, such a method is unreliable, but it is sometimes used to supplement the other methods described above. There is nothing wrong with line listings per se, but they should be checked by some form of automated process rather than manually.

The level and complexity of checks will vary from study to study, and will also tend to vary inversely with the number and complexity of checks carried out during data entry. Data centres exhibit wide variations in the emphasis they put on checking data during and after data entry, but they should have mechanisms available to do both, and be able to demonstrate both in action.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be:

- demonstration of checking procedures and/or scripts, and documentation of their use; and
- a discussion with centre staff explaining their use of post-data entry checking.

DM06.04: Query creation

Queries can be created – automatically and/or manually – based on any of the data checking mechanisms employed.

There are two main mechanisms for creating queries:

- during data entry, as a function of the omissions and discrepancies noted by data entry staff, usually prompted by the validation messages generated by the check logic in the CDMA; and
- after data entry, as a result of checking data, e.g. by batch validation or statistical methods, using values flagged in some way by the checking process.

In either case there should be clear procedures in place that guide when and how the queries are generated. Though not a requirement of the standard, ideally the centre would be able to always send queries to the clinical sites in the same way, whatever the query generation mechanism.

For instance, most CDMS include a mechanism for on-screen query generation triggered by data entry checks. It should be possible to manually add new queries, as identified by checks run on exported datasets, into the same system. The sites then only see the queries as presented by the CDMS.

Conversely a data centre running paper-based trials, where the queries also have to be delivered to the sites on paper, by post or courier, should be able to send the same query proforma for queries generated by the CDMS (used in-house for data entry) as for queries generated by statistical checking of datasets.

Evidence that the standards have been met would come from an examination of queries generated and a discussion with staff about how the relevant procedures worked in practice.

DM06.05: Tracking of queries

Responses are recorded when returned, identified when outstanding and queries resent if necessary.

Having sent the queries out, through an eRDC system or by post or courier, the centre needs to be able to track the responses to them and identify those for which no response has been received, or for which the response is unclear, resending the query or generating a new one if necessary.

If queries are sent out through the eRDC system, that system will normally have such tracking functionality built in. For trials using pCRFs a separate query tracking mechanism will be necessary. For best practice it would be linked to the query generation process and include functionality to prevent duplicate queries being sent out to sites, though this is not a formal requirement.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be demonstration of the query tracking system(s) that showed how queries were recorded and tracked.

DM06.06: Actions in response to queries

Query resolution is tracked, and appropriate actions taken and documented.

Once a query response has been received a decision is made as to whether it is fully answered or not, and a supplementary query sent if necessary. If the issue has been resolved, values in the CDMA may need to be changed.

For most eRDC systems with integrated query management the link between the query, its response and the value in the database, whether or not it has been changed, will be obvious and visible on screen. For pCRF-based trials with separate query management, many centres use a comment or 'reason for change' field to link

the data value to the query or queries associated with it (for instance storing a query ID number).

Either way the record of the query and its resolution should be linked to the data item, either in the CDMS or in a separate query management system, effectively making the query part of the audit trail.

The standard would be met if this is shown to be the case.

DM06.07: Self-evident corrections

Clear guidelines and procedures should exist to identify and carry out self-evident corrections.

In some cases the data on a paper CRF is obviously incorrect and would fire a warning or reject message if input, but it is clear what the correct data should be – the error has been caused by a common omission, addition or transposition. An example would be 07/11/208, 07/11/218 or 07/11/20018 for 07/11/2018, (albeit with an assumption that it could not be 07/11/2008) or the omission of a response to the ‘Any Adverse Events?’ question followed by a report of three adverse events.

In such cases it does not make sense to query the site, and a self-evident correction (or an ‘automatic obvious data modification’) can be used to amend the data. The use of such self-evident corrections (SECs) must be tightly controlled, however:

- They should be restricted to a pre-agreed list of situations where they could be applied, normally agreed at the level of the individual study (often starting with a default list maintained by the data centre).
- There should be a clear procedure to follow when self-evident corrections are applied, including instructions on how the source document should be marked to indicate that the correction has been made. SECs should be recorded transparently – those that are only deducible from an in-depth audit trail review are not acceptable.
- The procedure should include a mechanism that allows the investigators at the site to endorse any SECs made, e.g. sending each site’s final list of SECs back to the sites at the end of the study for review. A single sign-off to cover multiple SECs is acceptable provided the scope of the signature is clear. Note that the GCP requirement is for changes to be endorsed (i.e. approved) rather than checked. A pre-defined and pre-agreed set of pre-conditions for SECs, as described above, is, therefore, the most important component of SEC management.

Self-evident corrections could be applied to eRDC systems as well. But data entry checks should pick up the sort of obvious error that would call for a SEC and, even if something looked like it needed a self-evident correction, it could simply be sent back to the site as a query. SECs make sense for paper-based studies because queries are relatively expensive and time-consuming, but they are usually much quicker and cheaper to resolve in an eRDC study.

SECs are, therefore, discouraged in an eRDC context. An argument is sometimes made that before they can be coded, composite adverse event terms need to be split by applying SECs (e.g. ‘vomiting and diarrhoea’ turned into two distinct reports), and that this applies to eRDC systems as much as to paper-based trials. Even here, however, good training of site staff, and prompt querying of problematic data entry, should be able to resolve the issue without recourse to SECs.

Evidence that the standard has been met would include:

- the relevant controlled documents (e.g. examples of data management plans with self-evident correction instructions in them); and
- a discussion with, and demonstration by centre staff of the procedure in action.

DM06.08: Quality checks of data transcription

There should be policies and procedures in place to provide a quality check (QC) on the transcription process from paper CRFs to the database system.

(This standard only applies to centres running paper-based trials.)

Various approaches can be used. Some centres use double data entry of some form, for some or all of the data entered from paper sources. Others check accuracy retrospectively, for example selecting a sample (e.g. 10% of data, or particular visits/forms) and compare the database values with those on the original CRFs – a type of ‘internal SDV’. If the error rate exceeds a particular threshold, say 5%, the check is then usually extended to a larger size sample.

The standard requires that the centre has mechanisms in place to carry out this QC of transcription in paper-based trials. They may vary from one study to another, because they should be part of a risk-based approach to overall quality management, as determined by the sponsor (in accordance with GCP 5.0), usually in conjunction with the data centre, as the sponsor’s main data management ‘contractor’. The strategy is, therefore, likely to be described in a study-specific data management plan rather than in a generic controlled document such as a SOP.

The evidence for the standard would be the descriptions of QC mechanisms used by the centre, both in documents and as obtained from discussions with staff.

DM06.09: Quality check documentation

There should be detailed results available from the QC of data transcription.

(This standard only applies to centres running paper-based trials.)

The checks carried out of transcription accuracy, of paper CRFs, need to be documented. This includes the results, i.e. discrepancies found and decisions taken, of any double data entry.

The expectation is that at least a summary report would be available as part of the trial's documentation. The detailed data would often be available in electronic form and/or as a report from a system, but it should still be available on demand.

The evidence for the standard would simply be summary and detailed QC results.

DM06.10: Supporting source data verification

The centre has procedures for supporting source data verification, as a minimum providing access to its data for those implementing and conducting the SDV.

The sponsor will normally determine both the SDV strategy required and decide who will be doing the SDV. Pharma sponsors may, for instance, want to use their own monitors for SDV. Even non-commercial sponsors may wish to use a different trials unit for the monitoring/SDV function than for the data centre function.

What a data centre does need to do is support the work of monitors carrying out SDV, by making the trial data available to them. There should, therefore, be procedures in place for allowing monitors access to the data so that they can inspect and assess it, and for exporting and presenting data on demand, on a subject-by-subject basis, to monitors.

The evidence that the standard has been met would be the controlled documents describing the relevant procedures, together with explanations from staff about how they worked in practice.

DM06.11: Supporting central statistical monitoring

The centre can generate reports to support central statistical monitoring.

One of the key components of risk-based monitoring is central statistical monitoring of data, specifically to identify clinical sites which have relatively high query rates for their data, and/or which are consistently late with data. Centres should, therefore, be able to generate reports detailing query rates, missing or late data, and where appropriate additional study-specific indicators of problems during data entry, on a site-by-site basis.

The monitoring can also be used to identify particular data forms and even items that appear to give rise to problems in data collection, possibly prompting a redesign of the CRF.

The statistical monitoring may be carried out by using statistical packages and scripts against exported data, or it may come from reports built into trial administration systems if they handle data tracking and queries, or in some cases it may come from reports or audit trail review in the CDMS. The precise approach taken should be described and justified on a risk-proportionate basis.

The evidence for the standard being met would come from demonstration of the relevant reports and a discussion of how they were used in practice.

DM06.12: Removing fraudulent data

Data deemed invalid (e.g. produced fraudulently) can be safely removed from the analysis dataset.

Though rare, it sometimes happens that a site is shown (or is strongly suspected) to have produced data fraudulently, or is otherwise guilty of misconduct. In these situations, the sponsor may decide to disregard all the data from that site.

The expectation is that the centre could describe how (in a technical sense) the data could be safely removed, at least from the data being analysed – it would normally stay in the source data – and how (in an administrative sense) it would document the removal process.

Although a rare event, the centre should have documented guidance in place in place describing these procedures, e.g. escalation of concerns, whistle-blowing process.

DM07: Managing Data Transfers

This section deals with moving data files into or out of the data centre, normally to or from a different organisation. Transferring data into the centre is referred to here as *data import*, while transferring data out is described here as *data export*.

Data import occurs when centres receive bulk data, for instance from laboratories (e.g. biomarker data), instrumentation (e.g. the settings from a radiotherapy machine), collaborators (e.g. data from another set of sites), or even the sponsor (e.g. SAE reports). As depicted in Figure 5, It consists of two or three processes:

i1: Import of the data from the source organisation to the data centre.

i2: (Possibly) further processing of the data to enable merger with existing data and/or centre systems.

i3: Merger with other study data, usually by aggregating it with the analysis dataset, though it may be by uploaded to the CDMS, followed by extraction of the combined data.

Figure 5: Data import and export. The processing stages, i2 and e2, may not be required. The S denotes a point at which files should be stored for audit purposes.

Data export can occur in the context of a collaboration or meta-analysis, or sending data to a statistician or investigator based elsewhere for analysis or review. It includes the process of sending data to an external sponsor. It also consists of two, or more often three processes:

e1: An initial extraction of data, usually specific to a single study, from the CDMS or from the already extracted analysis dataset.

e2: (Possibly) further processing/formatting of the data to match the recipient's requirements.

e3: Export of the data from the data centre to the recipient.

Data import and export are, therefore, mirror images of each other, and their requirements are very similar.

DM07.01: Data transfer procedures

Controlled documents dealing with the transfer of data from and to the data centre should be in place.

This standard requires that there are controlled documents that describe the principles to be followed when transferring data, in either direction, including the documentation required.

In practice, a transfer process, especially if repeated, will often need more detailed procedural guidance if consistency is to be maintained. This is especially the case if the data needs transforming in some way, either before merger, or after extraction, i.e. the processing steps i2 or e2 in the description above are used. Generic procedures will, therefore, very often be supplemented by study-specific procedures, which should be described or referenced within the study's data management plan.

Decisions about who to send data to, and when, will rest with the sponsor or a trial management group acting on the sponsor's behalf. Similarly, the decisions about which laboratories and other facilities to use, and thus receive data from, will also be the sponsor's. In both cases, however, the centre needs to have procedures in place to ensure that it can transfer the data securely and accurately, and record the entire process, ensuring that it fully discharges its operational responsibility for the transfer process.

The evidence that the standard has been met would come from the controlled documents themselves and the documentation associated with specific transfers.

DM07.02: Records of transfers

Details of any specific data transfer should be logged, to maintain a complete record of how, when, and why data has been transferred to and from the centre.

Once the transfer takes place it needs to be recorded. Each data transfer log record should contain, as a minimum:

- details of the recipient (for data export) or sender (for data import);
- reason(s) for the transfer;

- a listing of the files received or sent (paths to current storage locations, see DM07.03);
- a summary description of the data, if not obvious from the above;
- the transfer method(s) used;
- the nature of any encryption used; and
- the date(s) of transfer and the personnel involved.

For data exports, it is also useful to request and then record confirmation from the recipient that the data has arrived safely and meets their requirements.

If the data is processed in some way as part of the transfer process, then:

- any scripts used for processing should also be retained (or referenced); and
- the details of the initial extraction (for exports), or final aggregation or upload (for imports), should also be recorded, e.g. dates, files involved, personnel involved.

This data, coupled with the retained datasets described in DM07.03, should provide a complete record of all data transfers. It can be maintained separately for each study, but is probably more easily organised as a centre-wide record. Each study's TMF should include a copy of the relevant transfer records, or a reference to their location.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from documentation associated with data transfers.

DM07.03: Retention of intermediate and transferred files

Copies of all files received or created in any transfer process should be retained within a read-only environment and be available for audit/reconstruction purposes.

In an import process the datasets originally received, plus those datasets after any required processing, (i.e. the datasets as merged with the existing data), need to be retained. In an export process the datasets as originally extracted, plus those datasets after any required processing, (i.e. the datasets as transferred out of the unit), will also need to be retained. The 'retention points' are marked with an S in figure 5. In that way the centre retains a clear audit trail of the data at each stage of any transfer process, which can be checked if necessary, and which complements the logging of the transfer and the description of any processing (see DM07.02).

To prevent any possibility, accidentally or otherwise, of modification of the data, the datasets should be kept in a 'read-only environment'. In practice this usually means within a folder where only a few staff (usually IT staff, because they are seen as

having no direct stake in the study or its results) can insert or modify files. For all other staff the folder and the files within it are set as read-only, and are, therefore, protected from amendment.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from demonstration of transferred data in an appropriate read-only environment.

DM07.04: Encryption of Personal Identifiable Data

Any file(s) transferred that include data relating to individuals should be encrypted.

If transferred data includes data relating to individuals it must be encrypted to the level considered as good practice by the national regulatory authority (typically 256-bit AES encryption). Because there is often difficulty in distinguishing patient identifying data from other data relating to individuals (see IT02.07) the requirement is that all individual participant data that is transferred is encrypted, and not just that which contains direct identifiers (i.e. fields that can obviously identify someone).

When data is exported the centre has control over the data and can ensure that encryption is in place. With data that is imported the centre must rely on the data exporter to encrypt the data, and the encryption cannot, therefore, be guaranteed. The expectation would be that the centre would work with the data sender to try to ensure suitable encryption was used.

In either case, preference is for a secure file-transfer (SFT) system, rather than reliance on attaching encrypted files to email – which may well be rejected by antimalware scanning software – or physical transfer of portable media (e.g. USB stick). Commercial SFT software is available and typically includes up-to-date encryption technology and full audit trail, i.e. who, where, what and when data was sent, and sometimes also whether it was accessed.

Evidence that the standard has been met would include the relevant controlled documents and explanation of how encryption of transferred data was carried out in practice.

DM07.05: Requests to amend previously transferred data

Procedures should exist to deal with requests for direct changes of previously transferred data.

This standard deals with a relatively unusual situation, and one that some centres may never experience. It involves the need to directly change a few values in data that has been previously transferred, and either bulk uploaded to the CDMS or aggregated with the rest of the analysis dataset.

It does not deal, or in any way suggest that it is acceptable, under any circumstances, to change data directly when that data should and can be altered via the normal user interface, by the normal data originators, i.e. the clinical sites. But such a situation can arise if data is imported in bulk (so there is no eCRF corresponding to it in the system) and it then becomes apparent that it needs correcting.

The easiest and recommended way of dealing with this situation is simply to repeat the data import with a corrected dataset. That provides a record of the data transfer process and the source files would be retained as an audit record. But it may be that the sponsor requests that the amendments are done manually on an ad hoc basis. An example might be an imported treatment allocation list (i.e. subject trial ID against treatment received, A or B) that had to be amended at the very end of the study because one or two subjects were found to have received the wrong treatment.

A centre should be either be prepared for such a situation, or prohibit it entirely and insist on another method of editing the data (e.g. by repeating the bulk upload). If the centre does allow direct data amendment, then because each change request will be different there is little a centre can do other than have a very generic procedure, for instance that identifies how the change request would be considered and by whom, who would carry out the action decided upon and how the whole process should be fully documented.

If direct amendment of data does take place then it must be recorded, with all details noted and communications (emails, etc.) retained, probably as a file note in the trial's master file.

The evidence for compliance would be the procedure itself and the records of any data amendment.

DM08: Delivery and Coding of Data for Analysis

The standards in this section deal with the ways in which trial data is prepared, checked, corrected, and then extracted in the format required for analysis.

The specific processes used for generating analysis datasets will vary, depending on the longevity and type of trial as well as the purpose of the analysis. For example, for a self-contained study where there will be no further data collection, the database is often locked down (or ‘frozen’, though the exact definition of ‘locked’ and ‘frozen’ varies between systems) so that no further data entry or amendment is possible.

For a longer-term study where data collection may continue for many years after the primary analysis, or where various interim analyses are necessary, it would be more usual to export a ‘snapshot’ of the data state.

Note that there is no requirement relating to the format of the extracted data. That will normally be as agreed with the statisticians who carry out the analyses, examples include CSV, XML, and SAS, R and SPSS native formats.

DM08.01: Policies for database locking

Controlled documents should be in place dealing with taking a snapshot of the trial data, and/or ‘locking’ and ‘unlocking’ that data.

All processes by which data is prepared and extracted for analysis should be governed by clear procedures, documented within controlled documents.

The relevant evidence would be the controlled documents themselves.

DM08.02: Data completion

All relevant data (or all except for a pre-defined/pre-agreed fraction) should be received prior to data extraction for analysis.

Extracted data need to be as complete as possible. In some cases database lock is dependent upon completion of data entry, in others a snapshot is taken once all data expected by a certain point is in, or at least – e.g. for an interim analysis – all that can be reasonably expected in a given trial at a given time.

The evidence that this standard was being met would be:

- the relevant controlled documents; and
- examples of communication and/or a checklist relating to database lock/snapshot and the levels of data required.

DM08.03: Query resolution completion

All queries (or all except for a pre-defined/pre-agreed fraction) have been resolved prior to data extraction for analysis.

Queries will also need to be resolved before database lock or snapshot. In some cases this will mean all queries, while in others some exceptions may be allowed. A risk-based approach should be adopted, prioritising endpoint and safety data. The rules governing any exceptions should be explicitly defined and agreed.

Data consistency checks will also often generate additional queries during the final phase of preparation for analysis, leading to an upsurge in query generation with, very often, faster timelines for their resolution.

The evidence that this standard was being met would be:

- the relevant controlled documents; and
- examples of communication and/or a checklist relating to database lock/snapshot and the query resolution required.

DM08.04: Data reconciliation

All external data (e.g. safety database, lab data) has been reconciled prior to data extraction for analysis (or all except for a pre-defined/pre-agreed fraction).

Data preparation may also involve reconciliation of the data input through the CDMA with that received from elsewhere, for example between expedited SAE reports and the more routine adverse event reporting, or between sample and laboratory result data. This should be brought up to date before the database is locked or a snapshot is taken. If exceptions to data reconciliation are allowed, they must be defined, agreed and documented prospectively.

Where data coding has been used (see DM08.07, DM08.08) it would be normal for that coding to be reviewed as part of the data preparation. In some instances a data quality check may also be done, especially if one has not yet been performed on this data. Whatever the detailed arrangements specified by the relevant controlled documents, a checklist dealing with the different aspects of data preparation can be a convenient way of ensuring all the aspects are covered and recorded.

The evidence that this standard was being met would be:

- the relevant controlled documents; and
- examples of communication and/or a checklist relating to database lock/snapshot and the need for data reconciliation.

DM08.05: Post-lock data amendment

Controlled documents should be in place detailing procedures to be followed if data needs to be altered after the snapshot or database lock.

Where amendments to the data are required after the database has been locked (and possibly exported), the preferred approach is to unlock, correct the data and relock (and export an updated copy). Such activity should be tightly controlled and documented, e.g. in the EDC system audit trail.

Where it is not possible to follow this approach – perhaps to correct errors that become known at the last moment, or to incorporate late returned query data – such cases should be explicitly documented.

The evidence that this standard was being met would be:

- the relevant controlled documents; and
- documented examples of post lock data amendment.

DM08.06: Read-only retention of analysis data

The data provided for analysis is retained within a read-only regime, and is available as a reference dataset for any future re-analysis or audit.

There will be a need to arrange for the long-term retention of any extracted data, partly for audit or inspection purposes, and partly to allow the reconstruction of any analysis using the same extracted data. This would normally be done by placing the relevant files within an area of the centre's storage capacity that is read-only (except for the IT staff who do the transfer).

The evidence that this standard was being met would be:

- the relevant controlled documents; and
- demonstration of read-only retention for a range of extracted datasets.

DM08.07: Policies for coding

If data coding is carried out, controlled documents are in place detailing the procedures to be used.

In many data centres some data is coded using international standard systems, usually as an aid to reconciliation, classification and analysis of data. The best known example is MedDRA for adverse events (and in some case medical history) coding, but other coding systems include the WHO ICD system for mortality and morbidity data and the WHO Drug Dictionary sometimes used for concomitant medications.

Using such systems involves more than the simple application of codes to matching terms. Code allocation may be ambiguous, and the standards exist in different versions, so policies and procedures must be developed to support consistency in coding and to stipulate the versions to be used, or at least how decisions about versions should be reached.

Autocoding mechanisms may expedite the coding process, but can blur distinctions between coding in different trials, so some centres prefer to set up autocoding for use only within one trial at a time. Clear policies should exist to govern the use of autocoding mechanisms, if they are used.

The relevant evidence would be the controlled documents themselves.

DM08.08: Coding training

If data coding is carried out, it is carried out only by personnel trained on the relevant systems with access to authorised trial-specific support material.

Applying codes is not straightforward so staff who do it need to be properly trained. Support material may be helpful, e.g. in MedDRA coding, a list of commonly linked symptoms to be coded as a single entity, and a list of such symptom pairs to be coded separately.

Common adverse events which can be classified in different ways (i.e. in MedDRA terms allocated to different system organ classes) may need to be listed against the classification that should be used – usually on a trial-by-trial basis. The responsibility for authorising such support material would normally fall to the sponsor/investigator, but the centre needs to ensure that such material is prepared and that staff know how to use it. Evidence that this standard has been met would be:

- relevant training records for the staff involved; and
- examples of authorised trial-specific material to support coding.

DM09: Long-term Data Storage

Trials eventually reach a point when data is no longer being input, all outstanding queries have been resolved and all the anticipated papers have been written. Direct access to the trial data, in paper or electronic form, is either no longer required or limited to occasional read-only access. At this point the trial enters long-term data storage.

The trial is not necessarily formally ‘archived’ or curated at this point. It could be, though very few data centres appear to have mechanisms in place to provide a full digital curation service for electronic data, even if many have separate long-term storage facilities (which may or may not be called an ‘archive’) for paper-based data.

The characteristic of long-term storage is restricted access and thus protection from change. The trial’s electronic documentation and its data become hidden or read-only (though some at least of the IT staff need to retain access in order to resurrect the data to active use if necessary). Its paper data records are moved away from the normal storage locations and into a special store reserved for old, no longer active records, which may not be at the same physical location as the rest of the centre.

Keeping electronic data over the long term may also mean changing the format of that data to make it less dependent on proprietary systems that may disappear in the future. Possible target formats are CSV files or XML, e.g. using the CDISC ODM format. The latter has the great advantage of being able to include metadata definitions as well as the data. Whatever the electronic format used for the data itself, associated metadata and other project documents (the protocol, TMF, analysis plans, etc.) must also be included in long-term storage, to provide the necessary context for full understanding of the data.

Anonymising the data can simplify long-term storage requirements because the data becomes less ‘risky’ if it is accidentally made accessible.

Anonymisation, and other de-identification techniques, also allows data to be shared with others, because sharing pseudonymous data (and almost all trial data is pseudonymised) is normally seen as requiring explicit consent, though regulations governing data sharing may change in the future.

At the moment the standards do not include the need for data transformations as part of long-term storage, or the need to prepare data for possible sharing on request (e.g. by de-identification), though they may in the future, especially as sharing individual participant data becomes a more prominent issue and the techniques required become more common.

DM09.01: Determining long-term storage

Controlled documents are in place that ensure that long-term storage arrangements, of both trial documents and electronic data, are agreed with the sponsor.

The final decisions about what should be stored, where and for how long will be taken by the sponsor, acting in the context of national regulations. It is important, however, that the centre's procedures include mechanisms to explicitly agree with the sponsor these three things, as well as the 'final fate' of both electronic and paper forms of data and trial documents – usually either destruction or archiving. The agreement with the sponsor should be in place at the start of the trial, and be part of the Data Management Plan, rather than being negotiated at the end of the trial when the data is ready to be archived.

This area continues to develop with an increasing tendency for funders to require sharing and reuse of data after trial completion.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be the controlled documents themselves, with a discussion of the types of long-term storage typically managed by the centre, and examples of agreements or contracts between the trials unit and the sponsors that covered this area.

DM09.02: Long-term storage of documents

Measures are in place to ensure secure storage and controlled access to paper-based records in long-term storage.

Some centres return all paper records to the sponsor on completion of all trials, because the responsibility of keeping records available for inspection is usually retained by the sponsor, and also because they may not have the room or resources to arrange for long-term storage of documents themselves.

If a centre does provide long-term storage for paper-based records, however, typically when the sponsor is its own parent organisation, then the storage facilities should be secure and include environmental protection (against fire, damp, etc.). Ideally, there would also be the ability to lock individual cabinets or shelving so that access to one group of documents does not mean access to all. In some cases the centre might make use of external archive facilities, or a service provided by their parent organisation, rather than storing documents within their own premises.

Access to the data in long-term storage should be controlled, usually with designated staff acting as the 'gatekeepers' to the stored material. This allows access to, retrieval and return of documents to be recorded and monitored.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be provided by inspection of long-term storage facilities, a discussion of access procedures, and the records of access and/or retrieval.

DM09.03: Long-term storage of electronic data

Measures are in place to ensure secure storage and controlled access to electronic-based records in long-term storage.

Long-term storage of electronic data is usually managed by removing access to it from users, except for IT staff themselves, effectively isolating the data. In most cases, therefore, data in electronic long-term storage stays within the normal storage capacity of the centre, but is just not visible to normal users.

Though such data no longer needs to be part of a regular backup procedure (because it is no longer changing) there is a need to ensure that independent copies of the data exist and can be accessed relatively easily if ever required. ‘Ordinary’ backup systems are usually configured to provide relatively short-term redundancy and security and are not intended to cope with long-term storage. Other mechanisms may, therefore, need to be used to provide redundancy in the long term.

Access to the data in long-term storage should be controlled, usually by IT staff acting as the ‘gatekeepers’ to the stored material. This allows access for individuals or groups to be managed and recorded, with restrictions reapplied when required.

Evidence that the standard has been met would be provided by a discussion of the storage and access regimes for long-term electronic storage, by the procedures described in the relevant controlled documents and the records of access.

DM09.04: Ensuring deletion or de-identification of data

Measures are in place to ensure that if and when data is required to be destroyed or de-identified, then the destruction or de-identification process applies to all copies of the data.

This standard applies both to data hosted locally by the trials unit and to that hosted by a third party, e.g. using a SaaS-based CDMS, where multiple copies of data may exist in infrastructures that are not directly controlled or even easily identified by the trials unit. The same principles apply to all data management scenarios.

If it is decided that data in electronic and/or paper form needs to be destroyed, the data centre should have procedures in place to ensure that the destruction is complete and recorded (e.g. by certificate). This applies both to the primary data, e.g. stored by the CDMS, and also to analysis datasets generated from them. For data or paper under its direct control this should be straightforward. For data kept within

an external infrastructure, perhaps accessed through a CDMS system, this means liaising with the data processors to understand where copies of the data are located and to receive documented assurances that all copies have been destroyed.

The practicality of destroying data within backup sets will be dependent on the nature and number of those sets (and should be one of the things considered when organising and costing backups). In practice, destruction of individual files within a backup set presents considerable challenges, e.g. when backups consist of entire server snapshots – common in modern ‘virtualised’ data centres – from which a specific file, perhaps within a database application or common data store, may need to be affected. Practically, many destruction policies rely on sequential overwriting of backups, though this may require many months to impact data (e.g. a daily backup on a 6-month cycle). Third-party providers often do not routinely provide confirmation or evidence of this process. The centre should, at the very least, be aware of the situation and able to communicate this to the sponsor.

One solution is to use a ‘customer-managed’ key (CMK) whereby the user implements encryption using their own key – as opposed to standard offerings which are encrypted but where the key is common to, say, the entire customer instance, and held by the provider. Provider-managed keys are – or should be – managed under strict contract (i.e. the provider undertakes not to decrypt data unless on express instruction of the customer). CMKs can provide assurance that the provider can never ‘see’ the data, and careful use of multiple individual keys, for each specific datafile or project, can offer a way to destroy data at this granular level, by securely destroying the key. However, there is a big caveat here: loss of a key means the data is gone, permanently – the customer cannot ask the provider to restore the data. This risk must be balanced against the limitations of destruction conferred by using third-party data centres.

If data needs to be de-identified (e.g. prior to transfer to a data repository) then, usually, only one copy of the data will require de-identification and other copies will be destroyed. The additional information that was keeping the data pseudonymised (i.e. that held the key to the identity of trial participants) may be destroyed, for fully anonymised data, or retained separately (for data that remains pseudonymous).

If the destruction takes place because the physical machine on which it is stored needs to be retired or disposed, then again the data centre needs to know how access to their data is made impossible. Local hardware can be securely destroyed though third-party companies, who typically collect a machine or disk and grind it to dust in front of the customer before providing a certificate or photographic evidence. Where a trials unit makes use of commercial data centre facilities controlled by others, ensuring that data wiping and disk destruction takes place requires liaison, transparency, and documented feedback from the data processor.

Dealing with commercial data centre facilities is part of the legal responsibilities of data controllers and processors and must be considered.

The relevant controlled documents, together with explanations of how they are applied in practice, would form the evidence that this standard has been met.

ST01: Treatment Allocation Standards (optional)

These standards deal with all forms of treatment allocation, i.e. both traditional randomisation, normally using permuted-block allocation, and minimisation and other deterministic methods. They are also concerned with the whole treatment allocation process, not just the parts supported by IT systems or IT and data management staff. Input from statisticians, in particular, is included in the scope of the standards.

If a data centre uses an external agency to provide some or all of its treatment allocation services, then it needs to have the evidence available that the external agency, where necessary, also complies with the relevant standards.

ST01.01: Procedures for treatment allocation

Controlled documents are in place dealing with the set up and management of treatment allocation.

Whatever the treatment allocation methods used, there should be clear policies and procedures in place governing how treatment allocation should be set up and then managed.

The relevant controlled documents would provide the evidence this standard has been met.

ST01.02: Policies for ensuring blinding

Controlled documents exist covering the preservation of blinding (where used).

Though not all trials can be easily blinded (e.g. surgery and radiotherapy trials, and oncology trials involving chemotherapy) most trials that involve only oral medication will be double blinded.

In such cases it is necessary to have clear policies about how blinding is established and should be maintained (these will often cover distribution of the labelled drug as well).

The relevant controlled documents, together with explanations of how they are applied in practice, would form the evidence that this standard has been met.

ST01.03: Policies for unblinding

Controlled documents are in place to support rapid and safe unblinding of blinded treatments when required.

Clear procedures are required, in the context of blinded trials, describing how, when the need arises, blinding can be removed. Unblinding policies should

normally cover the unblinding sometimes necessary for individuals, e.g. in the context of a SUSAR, and, as sometimes requested, for whole treatment groups, e.g. in the context of a data monitoring committee meeting.

If an automated unblinding system is provided by a trials unit then a backup system should be in place, e.g. by telephoning the trials unit who then access securely held paper records, or via records held at the investigator's hospital pharmacy.

It should be possible for an investigator to unblind a patient's treatment allocation without relying on sponsor or trials unit.

The relevant controlled documents, together with explanations of how they are applied in practice, would form the evidence that this standard has been met.

ST01.04: Algorithms and supporting systems

Systems used for treatment allocation are documented to show how they provide allocation sequences as specified and effective concealment of allocation.

The systems used for treatment allocation may vary considerably in sophistication, but they should be documented so that:

- The underlying algorithms are clear (or, if published, are referenced).
- The technical details of how those algorithms are implemented locally are available.
- The general (i.e. non-study-specific) validation of allocation systems is described, with reference to detailed results as necessary. This should include ongoing validation as the systems develop.
- The way in which the systems support allocation concealment is clear to investigators at clinical sites.
- The way in which allocation sequences are generated and managed inside the data centre, to ensure restricted access as appropriate, is also clear.

In other words, the standard requires that detailed scientific and system documentation, probably generated by statisticians and IT staff, is available for the treatment allocation systems. This is in addition to the material included within the related SOPs (the latter would traditionally deal with responsibilities, timing, outcomes, etc.), or study-specific requirements and implementation (see ST01.05).

The documents should cover the range of allocation scenarios the centre provides, e.g. blinded and open label trials, permuted blocks and minimisation. It is recognised that in some cases allocation systems may be relatively simple and that the documentation will reflect that. Nevertheless, there should be some statements about the aspects listed above.

If the centre uses one or more external allocation services, they should still provide and demonstrate familiarity with the technical/system documentation as described above, even if parts of that may have been obtained from the allocation service providers.

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from the documentation available.

ST01.05: Specification documentation

The treatment allocation system for any specific trial should be documented, tested and approved.

The broad methodology to be used for treatment allocation will normally be included in the protocol, but each trial will also have its own detailed specification, usually determined by the trial statistician (though the sponsor will have the final decision) dealing with such things as block size, stratification factors, or the random element within a minimisation scheme.

Once the allocation method has been fully specified it can be set up, either in-house or using an external service supplier, but in either case it will then need testing. The amount of testing required will be based on a risk assessment, considering, for example, the complexity of the allocation specification, its similarity to previous specifications and the previous use of/confidence in the allocation system. In most cases testing should be carried out by a statistician not directly involved in setting up the allocation system.

Once successfully tested there should be a documented sign-off against the specified allocation mechanism.

The evidence for standard compliance would be the relevant specification, testing and approval documents.

ST01.06: Problem management in treatment allocation

Any problems or errors that arise in the treatment allocation process are logged and the subsequent actions recorded.

Occasionally errors can arise in the treatment allocation process – subjects being allocated twice, or, if stratification or minimisation criteria were not collected accurately, being allocated to the wrong treatment group. Such cases, and the actions taken as a consequence of them, should be recorded.

The documentation of the allocation errors and the subsequent actions, together with relevant controlled documents, provide the evidence that the standard has been met.

ST01.07: Treatment allocation training

All staff who handle allocation requests are adequately trained for each specific trial randomisation process.

Treatment allocation is often complex and cannot always be completely automated. Where staff are involved, even if it is just noting down stratification criteria, they must be adequately trained so that errors do not occur (or are at least minimised).

Evidence that the standard has been met would come from records of training and explanation about how treatment allocation is distributed among staff within the centre.

ST01.08: Record of allocation

Records of all allocation material generated and all allocation decisions made must be maintained.

The treatment allocations made during a trial are a vital part of that trial's history and must be retained for as long as the trial data is retained.

This means keeping the original randomisation lists and seed, and the minimisation decisions in their correct order (i.e. context), and not just the resulting treatment allocations. Controlled documents would normally specify the process by which this data was stored, as well as the access control required.

These controlled documents, together with examples of the lists themselves, would provide the evidence that the standard has been met.

ST01.09: Failover to manual

System(s) must be in place, supported by training, to deal with a loss of IT-based treatment allocation (if used).

When treatment allocation uses IT there is always the problem of what to do when for some reason that IT system is unavailable. Treatment allocation should still be able to continue if subjects are presented for inclusion. A centre must, therefore, have systems in place to cope with this situation, for all trials being allocated at any one time, with the staff involved suitably trained to use whatever methods have been identified as suitable.

Manually allocating treatments from permuted block lists is usually fairly straightforward, but manually applying minimisation algorithms can be complex and may demand specialist expertise. In either case there will be the need to ensure that, once restored, the IT-based systems are brought up to date with any allocations that may have occurred when they were down.

The relevant controlled documents, training records and discussions with staff would form the evidence that the standard has been met.

ST02: Statistical Programming

These standards cover statistical programming, i.e. custom coding using tools such as SAS, Stata, R, etc., as part of data analysis, and focus on the data import and manipulation within the statistical software package, and validation of the software itself. Export of data from the CDMS is covered in DM07.

ST02.01: Validation of statistical software packages

Statistical software should be subject to risk-proportionate validation.

Statistical software used in the analysis of data is invariably commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) and widely used. Such software provides in-built support for common analytical functional, e.g. calculation of arithmetic mean, ranking, Chi-square.

Installation of statistical software should follow the vendor's documented procedure (IQ – installation qualification) and evidence retained throughout the product life cycle, i.e. including subsequent updates.

While it is important to assess the functionality of such software, the utility of testing specific functionality (OQ/PQ – operational/performance qualification) must be considered against its long-standing and widespread use.

A degree of due diligence is expected, for example, where updated software releases contain new functionality, not yet subject to years of real-life testing throughout the academic community.

For most common statistical software, however, this activity would be expected to be 'light touch' – the associated risk being considerably lower than those originating from custom programming and data transfers described below.

The evidence of compliance would be the inclusion of the software within the validation inventory with a description of risk and any associated validation activity, and review of product life cycle documentation.

ST02.02: Data transfers

Transfers of data into statistical software should be specified and validated.

Data typically needs to be exported from a CDMS, then imported into statistical software for analysis. There may also be manipulation of data after export and before import, e.g. in order to create the required import format. Each step carries risk which must be assessed, and appropriate validation applied.

Export of data from a CDMS will typically use standard functionality, which will have been assessed as part of the CDMS system validation activities. There should be

a clear specification for the export functionality, expected output data types and format, and associated test evidence confirming validity. This might be achieved using spot checks, e.g. comparing output data with that shown on eCRFs.

Manipulation of exported files should be considered a distinct process, covered by specific validation documentation. The nature of the manipulation should be defined in a specification, a validation plan covering the approach to testing, etc., comprehensive testing evidenced, and approval recorded. The process should be versioned and subject to formal change control.

Unwanted changes should be avoided, e.g. viewing exported data in Microsoft Excel then saving may inadvertently alter data formats – such viewing may be more safely executed using a simple text editor such as Notepad.

Import of data into the statistical software will typically use standard functionality. Again, an assessment of this should be included in validation of the software.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) should describe all processing of data, including CDMS export, manipulation, and import into statistical packages. Responsibilities of Data Management, Statistics, and IT should be clearly defined.

Evidence of compliance would come from viewing the DMP, assessment of documentation of statistical packages, and examination of validation documentation for interim manipulation.

ST02.03: Validation of statistical programming

Statistical programming should be subject to appropriate validation.

The statistical analysis of data typically involves a custom program, written by the trial statistician, making use of common procedures (e.g. formatting, crosstabs) and supported by the software package.

The analysis plan should be prospectively documented, based on the trial protocol. The plan should contain a risk assessment of the various components, and associated proportionate validation activity. A senior statistician should approve the plan.

Code should be subject to peer review, i.e. by a different statistician, and key outputs double-checked.

Programming should contain in-line comments, where the purpose of a particular section of code is not explicitly clear. Hard-coding of variables should be avoided and where used, should be clearly identified and justified.

Custom code should be versioned, and associated data exports labelled with this version and that of the statistical software. It should be possible to follow the path of

analysis and data outputs, particularly through subsequent runs, and after system updates. A key audit requirement is to be able to reconstruct and repeat analyses. Output datasets used in analysis or publication should be retained and not overwritten.

Evidence of compliance would come from viewing validation documentation; verification of statistical methods is not in scope.

ST02.04: Statistical programming guidance and training

Documented guidance for statistical programming should be available and training provided.

Guidance should be available covering programming good practice. This may be through static documents or use of dynamic wiki-type system.

There should be ongoing training of statistical programmers, both on use of specific software and on in-house procedures and documentation.

Evidence of compliance would be through review of guidance documentation and evidence of staff training.

ST02.05 Access to statistical datasets

Access to statistical datasets should be appropriately restricted.

Statistical datasets may contain sensitive data, due to risk of disclosure of personal details or treatment allocation (accidental unblinding).

Access to datasets should be restricted to those staff with a need. This includes data exported from the CDMS, datasets actively being used in analysis, and output data.

It may be useful to create defined roles for statistical staff, e.g. to cover those analysing data, reviewing data, and potentially unblinding treatment. There should be controlled processes for assigning and removing users from such roles.

Evidence of compliance would be through review of process and documentation.

References

- [1] Moher D, Hopewell S, Schulz K et al. CONSORT 2010 Explanation and Elaboration: updated guidelines for reporting parallel group randomised trials. *BMJ* 2010;340:c869 doi: 10.1136/bmj.c869. Available at <https://www.bmj.com/content/340/bmj.c869>
- [2] ICH. Integrated addendum to ICH E6(R1): Guideline for good clinical practice E6(R2). Available at <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/ich-e6-r2-good-clinical-practice-scientific-guideline>
- [3] C. Ohmann, W. Kuchinke, S. Canham, et al. Standard requirements for GCP-compliant data management in multinational clinical trials. *Trials*, 12 (2011). 85–10.1186/1745-6215-12-85. Available at: <http://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1745-6215-12-85>]
- [4] C. Ohmann, S. Canham, J. Dress, et al. Revising the ECRIN standard requirements for it and data management in clinical trials. *Trials*, 2013 (14) (2012), p. 97. Available at <http://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1745-6215-14-97>]
- [5] Cornu C, Donche A, Coffre C. Référentiel ECRIN pour la conformité aux bonnes pratiques de gestion des données des essais cliniques multinationaux. *Thérapie*. 2015, August 3. <https://doi.org/10.2515/therapie/2015042>
- [6] ICH GCP E6(R2) (see reference 2). Section 5.2.2 (page 23)
- [7] European Medicines Agency. Q&A: Good clinical practice (GCP). Qs 2 and 8 under ‘GCP matters’. Available at <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/research-development/compliance/good-clinical-practice/qa-good-clinical-practice-gcp#b.-gcp-matters-section>
- [8] Canham S, Crocombe W. Data on trial: what do DMOs require from their IT hosts? *International Clinical Trials*. May 2017, pages 38-41. Available (paywall) at <http://www.samedanltd.com/magazine/13/issue/272/article/4589>
- [9] EUR-LEX. General data protection regulation. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr.html>
- [10] ISO/IEC 27001:2022. Information technology -- Security techniques -- Information security management systems – Requirements. Available to purchase at <https://www.iso.org/standard/54534.html>

- [11] FDA. Guidance for Industry – Process Validation: General Principles and Practices. 2011. Available at <https://www.fda.gov/files/drugs/published/Process-Validation--General-Principles-and-Practices.pdf>
- [12] McDowell R. Understanding and Interpreting the New GAMP 5 Software Categories. Spectroscopy. Volume 24, Issue 6. Jun 01, 2009. Available at <https://www.spectroscopyonline.com/view/understanding-and-interpreting-new-gamp-5-software-categories>
- [13] Plagiannos C. What is GAMP5 and how do I use it effectively? Montrium. Available at <https://blog.montrium.com/experts/what-is-gamp5-and-how-do-i-use-it-effectively>
- [14] Ohmann C, Banzi R, Canham S, et al. Sharing and reuse of individual participant data from clinical trials: principles and recommendations. BMJ Open 2017;7:e018647. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2017-018647. Available at <http://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/bmjopen/7/12/e018647.full.pdf>
- [15] CDISC. Clinical Data Acquisition Standards Harmonization (CDASH). Available at <https://www.cdisc.org/standards/foundational/cdash>
- [16] FDA CFR 21. Part 11 – Electronic records; electronic signatures. Section 11.10 (e). Available at <https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/cdrh/cfdocs/cfcfr/CFRSearch.cfm?fr=11.10>
- [17] EU adequacy decisions. Available at https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/adequacy-decisions_en
- [18] Trans-Atlantic Privacy Framework. Available at https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/adequacy-decisions_en
- [19] Guidelines on computerised systems and electronic data in clinical trials, EMA 2023. Available at https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&ved=2ahUKEwiS3rOd9tr9AhWLR_EDHX2bDDUQFnoECBwQAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.ema.europa.eu%2Fen%2Fdocuments%2Fregulatory-procedural-guideline%2Fguideline-computerised-systems-electronic-data-clinical-trials_en.pdf&usg=AOvVaw3xiBZDskN8fFdN6uuVRnO8
- [20] GAMP, 2nd edition, ISPE. Available at <https://ispe.org/publications/guidance-documents/gamp-5-guide-2nd-edition>

Appendix A: Glossary

This section provides explanations of some of the terms and abbreviations used within the standards and supporting material. Many of these terms are relatively common, but because of that are often ambiguous. A more precise definition is, therefore, provided, at least for their usage in this context.

ADAM: The Analysis data model is a CDISC standard for describing and documenting analysis datasets, particularly in the context of regulatory submission. The underlying principle is that the design of analysis datasets, and the associated metadata and documents, should together provide an explicit description of the content of, input to, and purpose of any submitted analysis dataset (*see CDISC*).

Aggregated data: Data only about groups of study participants, as provided in statistical summaries and the research papers derived from the study.

Anonymised data: Clinical data from which the obvious PID (participant identifying data) has been removed. While such data often contains a unique identifier for each participant, that identifier cannot be linked to any identifying data. Anonymising data is a one-way process – once done the data cannot normally be linked back to individuals (*see also Pseudo-anonymised data*). It is difficult to guarantee anonymisation of data – in some cases clinical details, especially in the context of rare diseases, and/or linked geographical information, and/or linked genomic information, may allow the individuals who provided the data to be identified. Data is considered anonymised when the practical barriers to identifying individuals are so high that the process is impractical.

CDASH: The Clinical Data Acquisition Standards Harmonization is a CDISC standard designed to help standardise data collection, by providing predefined data fields for 18 domains, e.g. adverse events, demographics and others that are common to most therapeutic areas and phases of clinical research (*see CDISC*).

CDISC: CDISC, the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (<http://www.cdisc.org/>), is a global non-profit organisation that has established standards to support the collection, exchange, submission and archive of clinical research data and metadata. The CDISC mission is “to develop and support global, platform-independent data standards that enable information system interoperability to improve medical research and related areas of healthcare.” (*see also ADAM, CDASH, ODM and SDTM*).

Centre: Is used to refer to the organisation or team seeking certification as an ECRIN data centre, even though it may call itself a trials unit, a research centre, a clinical research department, a trials and statistics co-ordination centre, or any one of the

many variations on these titles. If there is a risk of ambiguity the term data centre is used.

Clinical data (or ‘individual data’, or ‘data relating to individuals’): Is used to refer to any data that is associated with an individual trial participant, whether or not it describes a clinical symptom or situation. In particular, it could include demographic, treatment and lab details – anything that is considered as relevant to the study and which is an attribute of a single study subject or their experience.

Clinical Data Management Application (CDMA): Refers to the specific system established to hold the data for a single trial. As well as the data itself, the CDMA contains the schedule and check logic for that trial, and the specific data collection instruments, i.e. the eCRFs, that have been set up for the trial. A CDMA is, therefore, a specific application of the underlying CDMS. The relationship between CDMA, the CDMS and the DBMS is described in the Introduction to section DM02.

Clinical Data Management System (CDMS): Within centres, the system (or collection of systems) that holds the clinical data gathered during trials. Often referred to as Electronic Data Capture (EDC) systems, CDMSs are often commercial software systems purchased from specialist vendors, but may be built and maintained in-house. Examples are Medidata Rave, OpenClinica, REDCap. Within the CDMS, each study will have its own logically separate CDMA (*see CDMA*).

Controlled Documents: Is the generic term used for all quality management documents that are authorised (i.e. signed off as correct and designated for implementation) by one or more people, and which are version controlled. They include SOPs and work instructions, and most policies. Most organisations keep their controlled documents within electronic filing systems and apply document management to differentiate the various versions. Because different units designate different controlled documents differently within their quality management systems the standards always use the generic ‘Controlled Documents’ rather than the more specific SOPs, work instructions, etc.

CRF: Is the generic term used for all types of Case Report Form (*see pCRF, eCRF, iCRF*).

Data relating to individuals: See *Clinical data*

Database Management System (DBMS): This refers to the underlying data storage system for a CDMS, often known as the ‘back end’ database. Almost all CDMSs use a commercial database system for data storage, e.g. Microsoft’s SQL Server, Oracle, PostgreSQL, or MySQL. Most use a relational table structure and some variant of SQL (Structured Query Language) to access and edit data and table structures.

eCRF: In the context of eRDC the electronic screen-based case report form, used for direct input into the CDMS from the clinical site. eCRFs normally include validation and range checks so that unlikely values can be flagged, and errors corrected, during initial data entry.

Electronic Data Capture (EDC) systems: see *Clinical Data Management System (CDMS)*

eRDC: Is the term used here for electronic remote data capture, i.e. data entry direct from sites. In most eRDC systems access for data entry will be via a web browser.

Guidance notes: See *Work Instructions*

iCRF (interim CRF): In many cases research staff cannot access eRDC systems while interviewing patients and/or collating information, or prefer not to, feeling it is disruptive to the interview and uncomfortable for the patient. In such cases it is useful to have a paper version of the eCRF, to capture data in a structured and accurate way, rather than simply making notes freehand. This paper CRF, probably printed from the eRDC system and used/retained within the clinical site, i.e. not sent to the trials unit, is here referred to as an interim or iCRF.

Individual data: See *Clinical data*

IT host organisation: The organisation responsible for managing a particular component of the centre's IT systems – exactly which component will vary with the context. To keep things simple, the body providing the IT component, which might be the centre itself, its parent organisation or an external host, are all referred to as the IT host organisation.

MedDRA: Acronym for Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities, used as a coding system for pathologies and adverse events in most clinical trials.

ODM: The CDISC Operational Data Model (ODM) is an XML format for interchange and archive of clinical research data. The model includes participant data along with associated metadata, administrative data, reference data and audit information. Unlike SDTM, which imposes its own structure on the dataset, the ODM can describe the meta- and clinical data in their original forms, for instance as stored within or extracted from a CDMS (see *CDISC*).

Parent organisation: Used to refer to that organisation (or organisations) to which the centre belongs – normally a university or a hospital, sometimes both. In some contexts it may mean in practice just that part (e.g. faculty, clinical directorate) which directly contains the centre, in others the whole organisation.

PID, Participant or Patient Identifying Data: Any data within clinical data that could potentially be used to identify subjects, either directly or by linkage to other

systems. PID obviously includes names and initials, but also hospital system IDs or national health service/insurance IDs, numbers which in conjunction with those systems would identify an individual. Dates of birth can be PID, though normally not in a large dataset and without other associated data (e.g. identifying source hospital) because unique identification would be difficult. There is no absolute definition of PID – it depends on the size of the dataset and what data is present. Any clinical data can be PID if it is rare, in a small dataset, or linked to other information (e.g. geographical location).

pCRF: The traditional paper-based case report form, distributed by the trials unit to the sites and then returned completed, usually by post or courier.

Policies: Fairly general statements of the aims of the organisation with regard to a particular aspect of functioning. Policies will usually be distinct documents approved by a senior manager or committee, and may or may not include a broad-brush description of how the policy should be carried out. Some policies may only be written down only as minutes of meetings, however, so not all will necessarily be formally controlled documents. Policies would normally trigger the production of supporting SOPs (*see SOPs*).

Pseudo-anonymised/pseudonymised data: Data from which the obvious PID (participant identifying data) has been removed, but which contains a unique identifier for each individual subject. That identifier not only groups and labels the data for a single subject, it can also be used as a key to link the data back to the subject's identifying data, if and when necessary. The identifying data must be stored separately (and normally more securely) from the pseudo-anonymised data. (*see Anonymised data*).

Remote access: As used here, is not the same as eRDC. It refers instead to the process whereby collaborators (including other trials units) and centre staff working away from the centre's premises gain access to the CDMS using technologies like Citrix, Terminal services or VPN, as well as browser-based methods. This may involve data entry, but could also include other functions like entering monitoring results, or even CDMA design. Remote access is, therefore, a more general term than eRDC, and can include a wider range of access methods and functionality.

SDTM, The Study Data Tabulation Model: A CDISC standard for presenting data for regulatory submission, and in particular to the FDA. It imposes a particular structure on the data, dividing it into specified 'domains' and specifying field names for data points within those domains.

Site: Used for the various clinical and other data collection locations that are participating in a trial and that provide the data to the centre.

SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures): Controlled documents, with version control and relevant authorisations, application/review dates, etc., which provide a description of procedures to be followed, describing and assigning responsibilities for the tasks and subtasks, and identifying the ordering, inputs and outputs of the processes involved. A SOP should be specific enough to be auditable and provide the necessary guidance to staff. They can often overlap with policies in scope, but are usually more specific (*see Policies*). SOPs normally form the backbone of any quality management system, with more detailed documents like work instructions and forms being linked to them.

Systems directly supporting clinical trials: This phrase, and minor variations of it, refers to all systems that store or process trial clinical data or analyses, trial administration and financial data, or trial-specific documents (e.g. protocols, agreements), i.e. all things that directly support trial activity and that would stop or disturb that activity if they malfunctioned. It excludes systems exclusively used for development, testing and training, and systems that only store non-trial-specific documents and data (e.g. general centre inventories, staff and budgetary information). It includes, however, mirrored or backup servers, even if they are normally passive partners, that could be called into immediate action as part of a failover mechanism.

Work Instructions (WIs): Also known as Procedures or Guidance Notes, these are the detailed procedural documents (or web pages) that describe how to actually carry out tasks. They are usually linked to, and referenced by, one or more SOPs. These documents should also be controlled (i.e. there should be a clearly defined current version), but may not require the full review/authorisation procedure of a SOP. For instance, an IT work instruction may be better revised and distributed by the IT manager, in conjunction with his or her team, rather than the full quality management team (*see SOPs*).

Appendix B: Differences between versions 4.0 and 5.0

Version 5.0 represents a moderate revision and includes two new sets of standards covering statistical programming and user device management. These and other substantive updates are summarised below. New standards and those with significant changes are shown in bold; standards with no changes, or where changes are trivial only (e.g. grammar, form of words) are excluded.

GE01: Centre staff training and support

- *GE01.04: Whistleblowing:* Renamed (was ‘Managing concerns – alternative pathways’); text clarified.

IT01: Management of IT infrastructure: Further details on use of commercial data centres added; RPO/RTO definitions added; expectations for commercial data centres added.

- *IT01.01: Infrastructure location:* Data protection legislation updated.
- *IT01.02: Secured server room:* Expectations for commercial data centres added.
- *IT01.03: Secured power supply:* Remit widened to include any computer infrastructure; expectations for commercial data centres added.
- *IT01.04 Controlled environment:* Renamed (was ‘...temperature environment...’); expectations for commercial data centres added.
- *IT01.05: Fire and smoke alarms:* Expectations for commercial data centres added.
- *IT01.06: System failure and response:* Renamed ‘System failure and response’ (was ‘Server...’); Emphasis on risk-based approach; inclusion of RPO/RTO.
- *IT01.07: Server support and recovery from downtime:* Simplified text; inclusion of RPO/RTO.
- *IT01.09: Server software maintenance:* New para re. risk-based decision-making.

IT02: Logical Security

- *IT02.02: Commitment to data protection:* Note of ‘adequacy’ added and widened scope of processing.
- *IT02.03: External firewalls:* Pen-testing recommendation strengthened.
- *IT02.04: Encrypted transmission:* Simplified text; encryption standard examples updated.
- *IT02.05: Server administrator roles:* Admin account use recommendations added.
- *IT02.07: Encryption of non-physically secured data:* Recommendation to encrypt all data at rest added.

IT03: Logical Access

- *IT03.02 Network log-in management:* Notes of MFA added; password advice updated.
- *IT03.03: Network lockout:* Manual locking recommendation strengthened.
- *IT03.04: Remote access (via VPN etc, not internet browser):* Scope clarified in title.
- *IT03.07: Administration of access to clinical data:* Notes on access to blinding information added.

IT04: Business Continuity

- ***IT04.01: Business continuity planning:*** BCP position strengthened; backup RPO/RTO and cyber-attack added; testing of scenarios added.
- ***IT04.02: Backup policies:*** Expectations for RPO/RTO, restoration practicalities, and used of commercial data centres added.
- *IT04.03: Backup frequency:* Reference to BCP added.
- *IT04.04: Backup storage* : Reference to cyber-attack and use of external hosting added; risk-based approach noted.
- *IT04.06: Recovery testing:* RPO/RTO reference and restoration practicalities added.

IT05: General System Validation: Inclusion of risk assessment; need to data centres to notify units of changes prospectively; evidence of sponsor responsibilities.

- ***IT05.01: Validation policies:*** Further examples of in-scope systems; use of risk-based approach; due diligence and vendor assessments.
- *IT05.02: Validation system inventory:* Advocate use of ongoing issue log as evidence of validation approach.
- ***IT05.03: Periodic review of validation:*** Validation of externally hosted services and prospective notification/documentation; evidence of sponsor oversight.
- ***IT05.04: Validation – detailed evidence:*** Focus on patient safety/data integrity risks; flexible use of GAMP processes and critical thinking; vendor assessments; validation of agile development.
- *IT05.05: Validation summaries:* Ongoing validation activity records.

IT06: Local Software Development: Risks associated with bespoke programming emphasised; statistical programming now in-scope of standards (see ST02 below).

- *IT06.01: Documentation of in-house software:* Specification now mandatory.

IT07 Management of User Devices: New

- **IT07.01: Device inventory:** New
- **IT07.02: Supported software:** New
- **IT07.03: Anti-virus/malware protection:** New
- **IT01.04: Device encryption:** New
- **IT07.05: Device disposal:** New

DM02: CDMA – Design, Development and Validation: Updated guidance waterfall and prototyping methodologies

- *DM02.02: The CDMA and the protocol:* All data flows must be described in the protocol.
- *DM02.03: Creating a full functional specification:* Specification must be human-readable (if metadata-generated).
- *DM02.04: Isolation of CDMA in development:* Updated description of CDMS vs CDMA environments.
- *DM02.06: Cross-disciplinary approval of the functional specification:* Mention of prototyping approach.
- *DM02.07: CDMA validation against the functional specification:* Updated description of testing/bug-handling; risk-proportionate approach; use of ad hoc testing.
- *DM02.08: CDMA final sign-off into production:* Minor updates.
- *Standards and reuse of items and forms as indicators of good practice in CDMA design and development:* Simplified text.

DM03: CDMA – Change management

- *DM03.01: Change management of CDMA:* Note re. suggested nomenclature.
- *DM03.02: Documenting change requests:* Use software management system for documentation.
- *DM03.04: Testing of CDMA changes:* Simplified text.
- *DM03.05: Versioning:* Suggestion for systematic versioning nomenclature.
- *DM03.07: Changes and protocol revision:* Change workflow emphasised.

DM04: Site Management, Training and Support

- *DM04.03: Isolation of training eCRFs:* Text simplified; use of dummy sites clarified.
- *DM04.04: Site access to production system:* Unique user accounts advocated.
- *DM04.06: Site documentation:* Change workflow emphasised.

DM05: Data Entry and Processing

- *DM05.01: Data entry policies:* SEC should be agreed prospectively.
- *DM05.02: Production of interim CRFs:* Use and risks of iCRFs clarified.
- *DM05.05: Handling patient identifying information:* Text simplified.
- *DM05.06: Audit trail:* Use of ‘reason for change’ clarified.
- **DM05.08: Audit trail review:** New

DM06: Managing Data Quality

- *DM06.01: Data quality policies:* Note re. wider scope of data collection.
- *DM06.07: Self-evident corrections:* Need for transparency and prospective agreement emphasised.
- *DM06.11: Supporting central statistical monitoring:* Inclusion of audit trail review.

DM07: Managing Data Transfers

- *DM07.04: Encryption of Personal Identifiable Data:* AES128 removed; advocate use of secure file transfer systems.

DM08: Delivery and Coding of Data for Analysis

- *DM08.03: Query resolution completion:* Risk-proportionate approach advocated.
- *DM08.05: Post-lock data amendment:* Preference to update in system emphasised.

DM09: Long-term Data Storage

- *DM09.02: Long-term storage of documents:* Return of documents to be recorded.
- *DM09.04: Ensuring deletion or de-identification of data:* Discussion of difficulties of deleting cloud-based data; use of CMKs.

ST01 Treatment Allocation standards (optional)

- *ST01.03: Policies for unblinding:* Need for backup system emphasised.
- *ST01.08: Record of allocation:* To include randomisation seed.

ST02 Statistical Programming: New

- **ST02.01: Validation of statistical software packages:** New
- **ST02.01: Data transfers:** New
- **ST02.03: Validation of statistical programming:** New
- **ST02.04: Statistical programming guidance and training:** New
- **ST02.05 Access to statistical datasets:** New